

DECO Activity Report (Year 3-4)

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August, 2024

D1.7: DECO Activity Report (Year 3-4)

Project name	Mountain Valorisation Through Interconnectedness And Green Growth
Project ID	862739
H2020 Type of funding scheme	Research and Innovation Action (RIA)
H2020 Call ID & Topic	H2020-RUR-2019-2 / RUR-01-2018-2019
Website	www.moving-h2020.eu
Document Type	Deliverable
File Name	D1. 7. DECO Activity Report (Year 3-4)
Status	Submitted
Dissemination level	Public
Date of creation	31 August 2024
Keywords	Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation, Multi-Actor Platform, EU MAP
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Acronyms

AEIDL: the European Association for Information on Local Development

CoP: Community of Practice

D: deliverable

DECO: dissemination, exploitation, communication and outreach

EC: European Commission

EU: European Union

GI: Geographical Indications

KER: Key Exploitable Results

KPI: Key Performance Indicators

M: month

MAP: Multi-Actor Platform

MOVING: MOUNTAIN Valorisation through INTERconnectedness and Green growth

MRL: Mountain Reference Landscape

MRR: Mountain Reference Region

RP: reporting Period

RR: Reference Region

VC: value chain

WP: Work Package

Executive summary

The deliverable **D1.7 DECO Activity Report (Years 3 and 4)** is conceived as a self-evaluation exercise that has the ultimate purpose of reporting and assessing the communication, dissemination and exploitation activities of the MOVING project.

This deliverable follows [D1.4 DECO Activity Report \(Years 1 and 2\)](#), and it is grounded on the final MOVING Strategy on Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation and Outreach developed in February 2024 ([D1.6 DECO Strategy – final](#)). In particular, this deliverable has two specific objectives:

- Analyse the performance of communication, dissemination and exploitation activities implemented by the project in years 3 and 4 and its contribution to achieving MOVING's objectives and Key Performance Indicators.
- Draw lessons, identify areas of improvements, and design actions and follow-up steps to be taken by the project to improve the communication, dissemination and exploitation activities.

The first three Sections of this deliverable provides an introduction to the scope of the document, a contextualization of the project and an overview of the methodology used to monitor and assess the communication, dissemination and outreach activities.

Section 4 describes communication, dissemination and outreach activities carried out by the MOVING project and its partners in Years 3 and 4 of the implementations. This section details the products, channels and methods used by the project, as well as synergies occurred with external channels and media to outreach a larger audience.

Section 5 provides a summary of engagement through the MOVING CODE Taskforce, and support provided to ensure more regional and local communication activities.

Section 6 assesses the impact of the project's communication, dissemination and outreach activities against its initial targets. Figures provides an overall successful picture of the project's impacts across all channels and products.

Section 7 concludes with the MOVING Exploitation Plan, providing a roadmap for the use of the project's results by partners in the medium and long run. The Exploitation Plan revolves around three Key Exploitable Results prioritized by the MOVING partners in view of their valuable contribution to increase the resilience and sustainability of Mountain Value Chains.

1. Introduction

MOVING (MOUNTAIN Valorisation through INterconnectedness and Green growth) is a Horizon 2020 project (2020-2024) coordinated by the University of Córdoba, gathering 23 partner organisations. The project aims to **build capacities and co-develop** - in a bottom-up participatory process with value chain actors, stakeholders and policy-makers - **relevant policy frameworks across Europe for the establishment of new or improved value chains** (VCs) that contribute to the resilience and sustainability of mountain areas in the face of climate and social changes.

MOVING project includes a Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication and Outreach (DECO) strategy (hereafter the 'Strategy'; [D1.1, revised in D1.6](#)) that aims to facilitate the achievement of project objectives and support all its activities.

The objectives of the Strategy are connected through a four-step logic. Firstly, the Strategy focuses on the **discovery** of the project by the target audiences, and aims to build a coherent, unique and recognisable structure of MOVING so the audiences become acquainted with its goals and activities. Following this, the Strategy's main attention shifts to promoting the **engagement** of key stakeholders. Progressively it focuses on the **dissemination** of outcomes and results achieved, to finally address the enhancement of the project **legacy**, especially by facilitating the uptake of its outcomes and results within and beyond the project's scope.

Inputs derived from the monitoring of the Strategy informs the project's internal reporting. Regular updates have been planned to allow the Strategy to evolve over time, as a result of new or emerging information, opportunities or trends.

The deliverable **D1.7 DECO Activity Report** is foreseen by M48 (August 2024) and it captures the communication and dissemination activities implemented from M23 to M47¹. This deliverable offers an update of the [D1.4 DECO Activity Report](#), which covered the activities undertaken by M1 and M22. The DECO Activity Reports in MOVING are conceived as a self-assessment exercise that has the ultimate purpose of identifying improvements in the dissemination, exploitation, communication and outreach activities and tasks tailoring them to the needs of the project, based on the experiences of the activities implemented so far.

The preparation of this deliverable includes the information and data presented in the second and third periodic technical report. This deliverable is drafted by the lead of WP1 (AEIDL) with the support of the project's coordinator, the Communication task force and the WPs leaders.

2. Objectives

This DECO Activity Report aims to take stock of the communication, dissemination and outreach activities implemented in MOVING during the years 3 and 4 of the project. Its primary goal is to

¹ The previous DECO Activity Report describes activities until M22. Therefore, these deliverable analyses and details activities occurred after that date. Furthermore, as the delivery date for the D1.7 is M48 (end of August), to be able to carry out an information extraction and subsequent analysis, the period that will be analysed until M47 (end of July).

assess their performance towards achieving the MOVING objectives. Additionally, this report aims at drawing lessons, identify areas of improvement and actions designed as well as follow-up steps taken by the project since the final version of the [DECO Strategy \(D1.6\)](#). Finally, it will present the final KPIs and pertinent data crucial to the project's overall assessment.

3. Methodology

This report has been produced using a **combination of quantitative and qualitative methods** for the analysis of the main MOVING communication and dissemination channels and products. This analysis and assessment were done gathering information from several sources. Data collection and analysis fall within the responsibility of AEIDL (WP1 lead), who have been in charge of monitoring the progress and propose corrective actions as needed to align with the project's outreach objectives.

A primary source of data collections has been the analytics' portal of the different communication and dissemination channels used. Among these, the most relevant been consulted were **Google Analytics, Twitter Statistics, Meta Business Suite, LinkedIn Analytics and Instagram Analytics, and the Virtual Research Environment**.

Additionally, the **DECO Monitoring of Communication and Dissemination Tool** continued to be used to track and monitor activities carried out by the project's partners to present the MOVING activities and results. This tool was also used to track the status of scientific publications prepared within the framework of the project. The WP1 Leader (AEIDL) was in charge of sending out regular reminders (every 3 months) to update the tool and reviewing the data.

As for tracking the progress and data from the Regional MAPs, MAP coordinators were asked to collect information on dedicated **Monitoring and Evaluation Tools**. Collected data were later consolidated by AEIDL and insights are further referred into the specific chapter on the Regional MAPs, under the MOVING Community of Practice.

Finally, a **survey** was carried out to assess the content and appropriateness of communication and dissemination activities, and their ability to deliver intended objectives and Key Performance Indicators. The survey, launched in January 2024 and remained open for 2 weeks, was conducted in line with the revision of the [DECO Strategy \(D1.6\)](#) and gathered the feedbacks of the projects' partners, particularly the Communication Task Force, – formed by at least one representative per MOVING partner.

A total of 22 responses from 21 partners were received. The survey results were used to assess, adjusted, and refined the communication and dissemination strategy for the final phase of the project. The survey provided insights into the effectiveness of communication products and channels, dissemination actions, adaptation of key messages, and prioritisation of target audiences. Detailed information on the survey results can be found in Annex I. Key survey results.

4. Communication and Dissemination activities

4.1. MOVING channels

The MOVING communication channels are selected to convey the key messages and outcomes of the project to the largest possible number of stakeholders and target group members. MOVING implements a series of communication and dissemination channels to reach the project's target audiences. This section provides an analysis of data and activities from Years 3 and 4, examining the efficacy of the different channels used by MOVING to communicate about the project, and its results.

4.1.1. Website

The MOVING website (<https://www.moving-h2020.eu/>) is the primary hub of information for the project, providing a 'one-stop shop' for resources, news, and key information on relevant initiatives. It links to and from the rest of communication and dissemination materials produced within the project. Launched in November 2020, and updated in February 2021 and August 2024, it has been regularly improved to better present the content and outputs of the project and make it more attractive to different stakeholders.

In Years 3 and 4, a total of **13 064 users** have visited the MOVING website (M48 target: 15 000). These numbers account for a total of **54 824 page views** (M48 target: 50 000). Hence, the website has showed good progress towards the targets set in the final DECO Strategy (D1.6). Figure 1 shows an overview of the visits to the MOVING website in Years 3 and 4.

Figure 1. Timeline of users visiting the Website between 1 August 2022 and 31 July 2024

Source: Google Analytics, consulted on 1 August 2024

The flow of users has been quite stable throughout the development of the project, including the last two years. Some peaks can be observed in Figure 1. For instance:

- On 8 November 2022 (84 visitors), MOVING organised its second EU MAP webinar.
- On 12 April 2023 (59 users), MOVING made available the Natural Sites Briefing developed by AEIDL.
- On 5 October 2023 (69 visitors), the third MOVING EU MAP webinar was held.
- On 14 November 2023 (63 visitors), the news about the highlights of the Cluster Workshop was promoted.
- On 22 February 2024 (93 visitors) MOVING shared on social media the call for contributions for the Scientific Conference in Cordoba.
- On 15 April 2024 (79 visitors) the vulnerability tools were promoted.
- On 14 June 2024 (753 visitors) MOVING held the second day of its Final Conference.

Overall, these events indicate the effectiveness of MOVING’s communication strategies in engaging stakeholders and disseminating project outcomes.

Apart from the homepage, the most popular web pages have been those presenting the MOVING Reference Regions, the Work Packages & Deliverables, and the News on MOVING or European updates. Table 1 shows the most visited pages of the MOVING website in terms of total page views, total number of active users, views per user, and the average engagement time (length of time users spend of each page).

Table 1. Overview of most visited MOVING webpages between 1 August 2022 and 31 July 2024

	Views	Users	Views per user	Avg. eng. time
MOVING - Horizon 2020	11 841	5 470	2.16	0m 24s
Reference Regions	3 548	1 187	2.99	0m 36s
Work Packages & Deliverables	2 790	1 545	1.81	0m 56s
MOVING news	2 046	331	6.18	1m 03s
Library	1 991	774	2.57	1m 02s
What is MOVING	1 976	1 255	1.57	0m 43s
Events	1 661	461	3.60	1m 00s
MOVING Partners	1 217	874	1.39	0m 44s
EU Multi-Actor Platform	912	455	2.00	0m 37s

MOVING blog	881	140	6.29	1m 19s
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Source: Google Analytics, consulted on 1 August 2024

There are several entry points to the website, i.e. organic search on engines (such as Google, Bing, Ecosia, etc.), direct entry by typing the URL², referrals from external websites, redirection from social media, and RSS feed (other), which are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Entry points to the MOVING website

Source: Google Analytics, consulted on 1 August 2024

The most relevant entry point is through Organic search (i.e. Google) representing 40% of users. Regarding organic social, most came from social media such as LinkedIn (3,7 % of total users), Twitter (2,9 % of users), and Facebook (4,3 %). And 1 % of users came from Mailchimp (platform used to send the MOVING newsletter and event invitations).

Table 2 lists the countries from which users visited the MOVING website. Seven out of the ten most popular countries are those from partners in the project. In six of these countries, at least one Multi-Actor Platform has been established.

Table 2. Users of the MOVING website sorted by country

No	Country	Users
1	Italy	1 803
2	Spain	1 436

² Direct traffic accounts for users directly typing URLs on web browsers, but also for unknown referrals (e.g. link copied directly on an instant messaging applications such as WhatsApp or Facebook Messenger).

3	France	854
4	Belgium	755
5	United States	695
6	Greece	573
7	Switzerland	558
8	United Kingdom	539
9	Netherlands	470
10	Germany	446

Source: Google Analytics, consulted on 1 August 2024

As Google Analytics only provides information on the country of origin and entry points for website visits, we cannot confirm whether the majority of users are consortium members or external participants.

Finally, according to Google Analytics, users have downloaded different PDF documents hosted on the website at least **5 912 times**³ (M48 target: **2 500**). This indicates that the target has been successfully achieved. The number of downloads has remained stable but shows higher figures compared to D1.4. Figure 3 presents the downloads of documents over the course of time, with peaks on specific dates corresponding to certain documents or information published:

- 27 July 2023 (83 downloads): Materials to promote the third EU MAP webinar ([agenda](#) and the [study on Natural Sites](#)).
- 31 October 2023 (45 downloads): [Highlights Report](#) of the third EU MAP webinar.
- 18 January 2024 (73 downloads): [Press release](#) of the MOVING European Foresight Workshop.
- 22 February 2024 (59 downloads): The document with the requirements to submit a contribution to the [MOVING Scientific Conference](#).
- 30 April 2024 (45 downloads): The [report](#) on the *Analysis of the implementation of the EU optional quality term “mountain product”*.
- 9 May 2024 (41 downloads): Presentations of the [4h EU MAP webinar](#).
- 19 June 2024 (43 downloads): [Press release](#) of the MOVING Final Conference.
- 23 July 2024 (45 downloads): The [Final Conceptual Framework](#) and the [youth engagement](#) results were promoted on social media, as well as the [Highlights Report](#) of the MOVING Final Conference.

³ Only downloads coming from the MOVING website are tracked by Google Analytics. Therefore, all downloads coming from different sources (social media, VRE, email, sharing among colleagues, etc.) are not counted as downloads.

Figure 3. Overview of document downloads on the MOVING website

Source: Google Analytics, consulted on 1 August 2024

To enhance user engagement and provide comprehensive information, several new pages have been added to the MOVING website between Q3 2023 and Q3 2024:

- **Results Section:** Presents the main outcomes of the project, linked to deliverables, infographics, or podcast episodes.
- **Our Tools Section:** Introduces Story Maps, inviting users to explore interactive maps on an external site, which highlight the unique attributes and challenges of our 23 selected Reference Regions, as well as the 453 value chains identified by MOVING across Europe.
- **Visual Tools Database:** Presents vulnerability levels, threats, and assets of all Reference Regions, making complex data more comprehensible through visual representation.
- **MOVING Mountain App Subsection:** Promotes the availability of this project outcome, offering information on where to download it.
- **Digital Stories Repository:** Features 23 concise videos, providing a comprehensive overview of the vulnerability of mountain value chains in both European and neighbouring countries.
- **Practice Abstracts:** Showcases all the Practice Abstracts developed by the project, each categorised by Reference Region and encompassing our project findings.
- **Policy Briefs:** Showcases all the Policy Briefs developed by the project, each categorised by sets.
- **MOVING Podcast:** “Conversations on Sustainable Mountains” is directly linked to the Spotify profile.

Upon the completion of the MOVING project, the website transitioned into a comprehensive archive, showcasing the project’s significant achievements and findings. The final version of the website ensures **efficiency and effectiveness in the user journey across the project’s results**. Visitors will be guaranteed with a simplified and more agile website structure, in order to

be able to identify the most relevant results for their target group. Furthermore, the MOVING's website will be kept alive beyond the project's lifetime, as set in the Grant Agreement.

4.1.2. The Virtual Research Environment

The MOVING Virtual Research Environments (VREs) are built on the D4Science Infrastructure⁴ by exploiting the gCube open-source technology (Assante *et al.* 2019a, Assante *et al.* 2019b). From the end-user point of view, this is accessible via MOVING Gateway (<https://moving.d4science.org/>). The Italian National Research Council (CNR) deploys and technically operates the VRE that support two-way communication with the members, exchanges, storage, social networking, activity trackers, and more functionalities.

Five VREs have been created during the project lifetime as shown in Figure 4. Two VREs are conceived to support the management of the project: Coordination Management and Project. The Regional MAPs VRE is used exclusively for the communication among the 23 regional MAPs' Coordination teams, while the EU Multi-Actor Platform VRE is open for stakeholders interested to exchange, learn and interact around the topic of resilience to climate change of mountain value chains. Finally, the StoryMaps VRE is conceived to build and share Story Maps on mountain ecosystems and value chains from the 23 Reference Regions of the project.

Figure 4. MOVING VREs available in the MOVING Gateway

Source: MOVING H2020

All VREs Labs (VLabs) include the following features:

⁴ D4Science Infrastructure: www.d4science.org

- A **shared workspace** to enable every user to store and organise the information files he/she is interested in working with. In addition to that, the user is allowed to collaborate with other users by sharing objects and messages;
- A **user management facility** to enable authorised users (i.e., VLab Managers) to manage other users using or wanting to access the VLab. VLab Managers can (i) authorise users' access to the VLab, (ii) assign or withdraw roles to users, (iii) remove users, and (iv) send messages to the current users;
- A **social networking facility** to enable users to use the common facilities typical of social networks – e.g., posting, commenting – yet adapted to the settings of working environments like those characterising Blue-Cloud. Users can post news as well as applications;
- A **notification facility** to alert users on relevant activities. These notifications offer a sense of anticipation and create a productivity boost. Users receive an alert (through the selected channels, e.g., email, web portal, Twitter) notifying them when something of interest has happened in their VLab(s);
- A **members' facility** to provide users with a list of VLab co-workers, i.e., the list of members included in the VRE and contributing to it;
- A **messaging facility** to provide users with a cloud-based common email environment. The distinguishing feature is represented by its integration with the rest, e.g., it is possible to send any information file available in the workspace (regardless of how “big” and “complex” it may be) as an attachment without consuming bandwidth.

Additionally, the StoryMaps VRE is equipped with an integrated tool (web application) capable of letting users build and share their Story Maps on mountain ecosystems and value chains. The tool is accessible at the following link: <https://dlnarratives.moving.d4science.org/index.html>.

An example of two (parts of) Story maps can be seen in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Example of two Story Maps available in the StoryMaps VRE

Source: MOVING H2020

The Story Maps VRE also allows access to the 454 story maps automatically created and reviewed by experts using SMBVT. The link is as follows:

https://dnarratives.moving.d4science.org/Moving_454_Storymaps/. The interface to access the 454 is shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6. The interface to access 454 story maps.

Source: MOVING H2020

Figure 6 presents the overall number of users benefitting from the facilities offered by the existing VREs. The five existing VREs Labs are serving more than 275 users. The detailed distribution of users on the VREs can be seen in Figure 7 and Table 3.

Figure 7. MOVING Gateway users from M25 to M48

Source: MOVING H2020

Figure 8. Users overview distributed by VRE from July 2022 to June 2024

Source: MOVING H2020

Table 3. VRE dedicated Virtual Laboratories and number of members

VRE dedicated Labs	No. of members
1. Project	135
2. Coordination and management	23
3. Regional MAPs coordinators	76
4. EU MAP	94
5. Story maps	76

Figure 9 reports the overall number of working sessions initiated per month via the MOVING Gateway. From July 2022 to June 2024, there is a notable peak in October 2022 with 619 sessions, and an overall average of 328 sessions per month. Working sessions are connections or access to VREs.

Figure 9. MOVING Gateway working sessions

Source: MOVING H2020

The MOVING Gateway is also used as a repository of files that are managed in the common Workspace; a social space where messages can be posted to all members of one or more VREs Labs; a secure and confidential email system where users can exchange private messages with other registered users without knowing their private email addresses.

Figure 10 reports the overall workspace sessions initiated per month by the MOVING users. Workspace sessions are the connection/access to the MOVING Cloud repository of files (workspace). Figures 11 and 12 report the overall exploitation of the Social Interaction facilities.

Figure 10. MOVING VRE workspace sessions

Source: MOVING H2020

Figure 11. MOVING VRE Social Interaction posts

Source: MOVING H2020

Figure 12. MOVING VRE Social Interaction likes

Source: MOVING H2020

In Figures 13 and 14, the geographical distribution of the users accessing the MOVING Gateway is reported. Figure 13 shows the European map coloured according to the average session duration expressed in seconds, while Figure 14 shows the map coloured according to the total number of page views.

Figure 13. Geographical distribution of the users accessing the MOVING Gateway – Europe Sessions

Source: MOVING H2020

Figure 14. Geographical distribution of the users accessing the MOVING Gateway – World Sessions

Source: MOVING H2020

4.1.3. The MOVING Community of Practice

A core feature of the project is the creation and animation of the [MOVING Community of Practice \(CoP\)](#). The MOVING CoP is understood as a **European-wide Science-Society-Policy interface to engage stakeholders around resilience to climate change, and other threats, of mountain value chains** and bring together interested stakeholders to contribute to the co-creation and validation of all research outputs delivered by MOVING.

The MOVING CoP is the main forum for **two-way peer exchanges** of ideas for **co-learning and co-creation of knowledge** with different stakeholders (MOVING partners and externals to the project) and at different territorial level (regional and European). The conceptualisation of the MOVING CoP is transferred into practice through the creation of Multi-Actor Platforms (MAPs), that provide the space for interaction, exchange and learning with stakeholders of the community at all territorial levels (regional and European). Hence, MOVING has created, animated and facilitated 24 MAPs across Europe:

- [23 regional MAPs](#), established in the 23 Reference Regions; and
- [1 EU-level MAP](#).

Figure 15 represents graphically the structure of the CoP with different levels of interaction in the project.

Figure 15. Structure of the MOVING CoP

Source: MOVING H2020

Following the integrated transdisciplinary approach of the MOVING project, the MAPs provide a platform and space to engage with relevant stakeholders in the different activities of the project. This allows the exchange of knowledge and peer learning between stakeholders from the Reference Regions (RR) up to the European level.

Under WP1, AEIDL has developed a Monitoring and Evaluation Tool for MAPs that helps to:

- keep track of and reflect on the performance and engagement of the MAPs.

- capture and record the needed information that feeds into deliverables and the reporting on the progress of the objectives achieved and measurable impacts of the project overall.

Regional MAPs

The 23 regional MAPs are established in the **23 Reference Regions covering 16 countries**. These regions represent the wide diversity of mountain areas in Europe and neighbouring countries. Each of the regional MAPs are implemented, animated and facilitated by the coordinators of each Reference Region.

Figure 16. Distribution of MOVING Reference Regions

Source: MOVING H2020

During the last two years of the project the regional MAPs members have participated and developed the following activities:

- Task 4.5 Vulnerability, sustainability assessment and resilience appraisal
- Task 1.5 Youth engagement meetings
- Task 6.2 Foresight workshops

The total number of actors involved by the 23 regional MAPs is **1107** stakeholders⁵ of **which 63% are men and 37% are women**. Figure 17 shows the distribution of the total number of members by actor type. As can be seen, the most represented types of actors are: Other (28%), Public authority/policy maker (17%), producer and producer associations (13%), researchers (12%), business (agricultural) (11%). To a lesser extent, representations from the following groups is recorded: business (diversified or non-agricultural businesses) (6%), innovation broker/advisor (5%), NGO/CSO (5%), civil society (3%).

⁵ The total number of stakeholders engaged is computed as a sum of participants for each activity organised. In some regions, the same actors participated to more than one activity.

Figure 17. Regional MAPs' composition by Month 42, June 2024 (type of actor, n =1077)

Source: MOVING H2020

Figure 18 illustrates the progress of MAPs composition by M22 (June 2023), M34 (June 2023) and M46 (June 2024). The total number of actors engaged increased over time, coherently with the number of activities carried out per period. In between M35 and M46, a large number of 'Others' is recorded, as it was used to identify young participants engaged in Task 1.5 and not identifiable in other actor categories.

Figure 18. Regional MAPs composition progress (by type of actors) by M22 (n= 766), M34 (n= 912) and M46 (n=1077)

Source: MOVING H2020

The following figures show the total number of members of the regional MAPs by: a. (Figure 19) geographic area of influence (local or reference landscape/RL, regional or reference region/RR, national and other); b. (Figure 20) level of participation and involvement (core group, active participants and occasional or associated participants) and c. (Figure 21) age (under 25, 25 to 40 and over 40 years of age).

Figure 19 Regional MAPs' composition (area covered, n=1077)

Source: MOVING H2020

Figure 20. Regional MAPs' composition (level of participation, n=1077)

Source: MOVING H2020

Figure 21. Regional MAPs' composition (participants' age, n= 1077)

Source: MOVING H2020

Table 4 provides an overview of regional MAPs activities in Year 3 and 4. It includes the number of events organised, the number of participants and the number of stakeholders interviewed for tasks 1.5, 4.5 and 6.2.

Table 4. Regional MAPs activities in Year 3 and 4

Task	Number of events	Number of participants
Task 1.5 Youth engagement meetings	54	1112
Task 4.5 Vulnerability, sustainability assessment and resilience appraisal	23	219
Task 6.2 Foresight workshops	54	286
Other non-mandatory events (meetings, discussion groups, visits)	7	138
Total	138	1755

Source: MOVING H2020

Additionally, Table 5 provides an overview of actor types involved by Regional MAPs in tasks 4.5, Task 1.5 and Task 6.2. The composition of actor groups varies sensibly across tasks. In Task 4.5, the largest stakeholder groups are: producers and producers associations (22%), agricultural businesses (19%), policy authority and policy makers (17%) and researchers (17%). In Task 1.5, the largest groups are by far “Others” (49%), representing mainly young students and youngsters

which were not captured by other stakeholder categories. As for Task 6.2, public authorities/policy makers equal 27% of all participants, followed by researchers (20%) and agricultural businesses (12%).

Table 5. Percentage of type of stakeholders in the regional MAPs activities in Year 3 and 4

Task	Task 4.5	Task 1.5	Task 6.2
Public authority/policy-maker	17%	1%	27%
Researcher	17%	2%	20%
Business (agricultural)	19%	1%	12%
Business (diversified or non-agricultural business)	6%	1%	9%
Innovation broker/advisor	9%	-	7%
Producer & producers associations	22%	5%	11%
NGO/CSO	3%	1%	9%
Civil society	2%	40%	2%
Other	5%	49%	3%

Source: MOVING H2020

In addition, by the means of a dedicated monitoring and evaluation tool for regional MAPs, AEIDL could gather **qualitative data of the 23 MAP Coordinators** on the **multi-actor process in MOVING, MAP composition and methodology, as well as the specific activities** carried out in these last two years of implementation. In Years 3 and 4, Reflections from MAP coordinators were collected by M34 (June 2023) and M46 (June 2024).

On the MAP coordinators were asked to share the **MAP members' expectations** from their involvement in the process. It emerged:

- Actors' expectations are quite diverse and strongly intertwined with triggering an improvement of the regional Value Chain or related challenges (e.g. improve olive groves, deal with large carnivores, develop wool value chain).
- However, most MAP participants are interested in finding concrete solutions on territorial challenges that they do not have time to deal with in their day-to-day management and pilot them. Furthermore, actors stressed other interests: networking (local/regional collaboration & European level), contributions to policymaking with recommendations

based on findings (“voice to be heard”), resolving local challenges and contributing to socio-economic development of the areas.

- Towards the end of the project, several MAPs emphasized the participants’ interest in thinking about the long-lasting continuation of the project and how to make use of results for the benefit of the area.

The **main barriers** identified by MAP coordinators over the last two years of the project are mentioned below:

- As for the first years of implementation, the following barriers persist: limited time availability by MAP members, travelling distance to reach the meeting points.
- Time is particularly mentioned as the biggest barrier hindering actor involvement, in particular of farmers and producers, in the MAP activities.
- Some MAP coordinators underline the discontinuity of actor engagement and the difficulty to keep them motivated over time.
- In some MAPs, stakeholder participation reached their own stability over these last two years, with core group and other rotating around and being interested, keeping interest over time, repetitiveness of project’s activities over time.

The **composition of MAP groups and its implications on group dynamics** was investigated by a set of specific questions.

- The large majority of MAPs included a heterogeneous and balanced group of stakeholders selected on the basis of their relevance on the topics discussed. A few underrepresented actor profiles were identified (see question below).
- In some cases, the MAP composition impacted on group dynamics. For instance, it was noted that producers felt having less status than researchers or technicians, sometimes making more difficult for them to express their opinion, or that imbalances on gender composition sometimes led women to speak less than men.
- Some MAP coordinators mentioned that teamwork in smaller and diversified groups, as well as different forms to collect participant feedback (e.g. surveys) were used to ensure equal participation by all.
- In most MAP, activities – especially in-person ones- fostered new interactions among different types of stakeholder groups. In many cases, MAP members already knew each other.

The MAP coordinators pointed out that the following **actor groups were underrepresented** in some of the MAPs:

- The most mentioned underrepresented actors by MAP coordinators were women and youth, organic producers, retailers and marketing actors, farmers/food processors (lack of time), CSOs/NGOs.
- Many MAP coordinators described their Value Chain as male-dominated sector, and because of that, it was quite difficult to find and engage women in the entire process.
- In some specific cases, MAP found hard to involve researchers and park managers.

- A few MAP coordinators had trouble engaging with the national level.

The **most important lessons learned from the MAP settings** are listed below:

- MAP coordinators praised the multi-actor approach as an open space providing a framework for discussion, networking and collaboration based on the values of trust and closeness.
- Several key ingredients to ensure a successful implementation of the MAP process were mentioned. In particular, MAP coordinators underlined: i) the human factor, as crucial to facilitate engagement and work flow; ii) the role of MAP coordinator, in providing a group vision and setting a cohesive plan with realistic expectations; iii) the MAP composition, and particularly the importance to select key actors in the region for building up the MAP and including 'knowledge' partners, both from academia and local 'knowledgeable' partners.
- It was recalled the high complexity and time-consuming task of building up and animating multi-actor group. Big efforts are needed to contextualize discussions and align with actor interests.
- However, almost the entirety of MAPs strongly agreed on the long-term added value of hearing and mixing different perspectives on a matter and its ability to create a conducive environment for collective learning and community building.
- The Importance of integrating conflict resolution methods and person was mentioned by some MAPs.
- Some MAP coordinators underscored the importance of linking the reflection process with MAP mobilization in order to ensure concrete improvements of the regional Value Chain.
- Showing results towards the end is crucial to deliver a sense of accomplishment in the journey and use them for lobbying/advocacy to give them 'a light at the end'.

A question was asked on the **appropriateness of supporting tools and information** used to facilitate the MAP coordinators' role and entire MAP process, and whether other tools might have been needed to improve MAP performance:

- About half of the MAPs used the engagement guidelines provided by the project and found them useful to different extents. The remaining half already had other guidelines or expert coordinator for engagement.
- Other needed information mentioned by MAP coordinators to facilitate the process included: data-needed information, technical support and simplification of results.
- Several MAPs mentioned the need to improve the communication channels with local actors within the MAP to exchange information and experiences.
- A large share of MAP coordinators highlights the need to foresee a compensation method (monetary or other) for the 'time' spent by participants on activities.

In addition, MAP coordinators were requested to reflect on the rolling out of activities occurred in the last two years of the project in order to foster collective learning and potential adjustments over time.

On Task 1.5 “**Engaging young people in MOVING activities**”, the following considerations from MAP coordinators were collected:

- Several MAP coordinators did not have former experience in engaging with youth. However, the large majority expressed high positiveness of this task, characterized by high engagement of the youth and constructive discussions.
- Outputs from youth discussions were diverse, going from general positivism to mountain situation to quite pessimistic thoughts about the future of the mountains. In some MAPs, very few youths were living specifically in the mountains or had specific knowledge of mountain Value Chains.
- The most common topics of interest by mountain youth were: employment and living wages, availability and quality of public services (e.g. transport), economic diversification and training, the provision of a vibrant social and cultural life in the villages, environment.
- On the question ‘How would or could youth like to contribute to the sustainability of their mountain region?’, several ideas were brought up ranging across trainings on policy, volunteering, eco-tourism alternatives, digital innovation, more informed consumer awareness.
- In several MAPs, it was recalled the importance to strengthen place-based knowledge and trainings, and to integrate sustainability into local educational program as a horizontal module.
- It was mentioned that mechanisms to encourage youth people to remain in the mountains should be not only financial but should also include social aspects, better training opportunities.

On the MAP activities carried out under **Task 4.5 “Vulnerability, Sustainability Assessment and resilience Appraisal”**, MAP coordinators emphasized the following points:

- The concepts of vulnerability, sustainability, assessment and resilience appraisal were presented all along the workshops. Most MAPs stressed the difficulty of translating such concepts into laypeople language.
- More complex and derived concepts of ‘exposure’ and ‘sensitivity’ were not understood by participants in some of the MAPs. In some cases, regional stakeholders were already aware about those concepts or well understood them without major issues.
- Overall, the use of practical examples facilitated the understanding and conveying of these concepts.
- In most of MAPs, the identification of adaptive capacity mechanisms and preconditions was easy for some MAPs, yet there were some MAPs where the exercise was very difficult.
- Even for the regions where adaptive capacity occurred easily, some MAP coordinators stressed that participants did not believe the change or were seeking for outside support. National or EU policies were seen as crucial to bring support.

- In some cases, it was highlighted that conflictual interests, administrative barriers or limited funds might hinder the ability to improve identified adaptive mechanisms and unleash related skills.

On **Task 6.2 “Local, Cross-case and Pan-European foresight Workshops”**, the following considerations emerged:

- The diversity of participants (multi-actor approach) was mostly seen as very positive, as stakeholders could angle their contribution under different perspectives and build converging scenarios. In one case, conflicts arose.
- In some cases, local foresight workshops did not achieve or had limited involvement of specific user hard-to-involve groups, e. g. farmers or producers.
- Methodology and guidance provided were deemed useful, contributing to establish creative thinking, cohesion among members and a ‘safe’ space for speaking, boosting networking. Scenario visualization, working techniques and engaging methods along the workshops were praised by MAP coordinators.
- In some cases, it was said that the preparation of local foresight workshop required a lot of preparatory work by MAP coordinators and dedicated time for participation and travelling for MAP members, who hindered its efficacy.
- Most MAP coordinators declared that the workshop did not help them to identify knowledge gaps and research areas, but it was useful to identify particular data needs or variables/indicators required by local actors. Further, some of them said it was useful to identify policy needs.

EU MAP

The [MOVING EU MAP](#) is the **EU-level component of the project’s Community of Practice**. It offers an open space to stakeholders (from policy, research and relevant practice groups) that are interested to exchange, learn and interact at the EU level on resilience and sustainability of mountain value chains.

The total number of EU MAP members is 94 stakeholders, out of which 57% are women and 43% are men. As shown in Figure 22, approximately half of its components comes from academia and research organisations, while the second largest stakeholder groups are from NGO/association/foundation (20%). The remaining share is almost equally divided across different other types of stakeholder groups.

Figure 22. EU MAP composition (type of actor, =94)

Source: MOVING H2020

The main activities carried out by the EU MAP in Years 3 and 4 are presented below:

Second EU MAP webinar on “European Quality schemes: the added value for mountain value chains” (8 November 2022). MOVING held its on *European Quality schemes: the added value for mountain value chains* on 8 November 2022. The event aimed to:

- Find out more about MOVING project results and the EU MAP;
- Provide an update of the new EU quality policy, according to the EC legislative proposals;
- Inform about the implementation and added value of the EU quality schemes and the implications for mountain value chains;
- Enhance the exchange, learn and interact at the EU level on the application to mountain value chains.

The event featured presentations on the progress and achievements of the MOVING project over its first two years, including insights from its Community of Practice (CoP). A representative from the European Commission discussed the new proposals' benefits for producers and their implications for mountain value chains. Additionally, partners from the Association of European Regions for Products of Origin (AREPO) shared their position and policy **recommendations on revising the EU Geographical Indications System (GIs)**, noting the current system's lack of a sustainability definition. The benefits and implementation of the **EU optional quality term "mountain product"** were also addressed.

Contributions were made by mountain value chains from four MOVING [reference regions](#), demonstrating the quality schemes' impact on different value chains: (i) Serra da Estrela PDO Cheese value chain (Cordilheira Central); (ii) Alto-Molise Dairy value chain (Central Apennines),

(iii) Trento PDO Wine value chain (Eastern Alps), and (iv) Sjenica lamb PDO value chain (Dinaric Mountains).

The event gathered around 60 attendees from different backgrounds (research, public authorities, advisors, business, producers, other EU-funded projects, etc.), representing over 15 countries. All the [presentations](#) and [recordings](#) of the webinar are available on the [event page](#). The [highlights report](#) is available on the website and in [Zenodo](#).

Briefing: “Protected natural sites in MOVING regions: Implications and added value for mountain value chains”

Inspired by the declaration of the International Year of Sustainable Mountain Development in 2022 and the relaunch of the World Network of Mountain Biosphere Reserves by UNESCO’s Man and the Biosphere Programme (MAB), the MOVING EU MAP undertook a survey among its [23 Reference Regions](#). The goal was to identify the presence of various protected natural sites within these regions and to provide informative insights on their added value and development implications for the MOVING regions and their selected value chains.

To achieve this, data collection was conducted during March and April 2022. Information was gathered from the 23 reference regions and compiled into a detailed [briefing](#), available on the project’s website and [Zenodo](#).

The finding from this study, conducted by partners from AEIDL (European Association for Innovation in Local Development), informed the preparation of the 3rd EU MAP webinar, which focused on the role and impact of protected natural sites on mountain value chains and were presented at the 3rd European Rural Geographies Conference 2023.

Third EU MAP webinar on “Protected natural sites: A constraint or an opportunity for mountain value chains?” (5 October 2023). MOVING held its [third EU MAP webinar on Protected natural sites: A constraint or an opportunity for mountain value chains?](#) on 5 October 2023. The event aimed to:

- Provide an update about the Nature Restoration Law in Europe;
- Provide information on the protection of nature in the mountains;
- Explore the findings of MOVING’s study on how the presence of protected natural sites impacts value chains across the 23 mountain regions;
- Exchange knowledge, practices, and lessons learned on the implications that the presence of protected areas has on mountain value chains;
- Present the MOVING project’s progress and results and publicize the EU MAP.

The webinar included a presentation from MOVING’s coordinator on the project’s progress and latest results, and another from MOVING Cluster N (‘Nature and Ecosystem Services’) that highlighted the value of nature for mountain value chains in the Sumava Region, Czechia. Key presentations also featured two MOVING regions: the Austrian Alps and the Southern Romanian Carpathian Mountains. These regions demonstrated the close relationship between natural sites and their mountain value chains.

Additionally, there were three presentations by external experts on: (i) Progress and updates on the Nature Restoration Law, (ii) National Restoration Plans and their implementation at the Member State level, and (iii) Insights from the World Network of Mountain Biosphere Reserves. Results from the MOVING study on the impacts of protected natural sites in MOVING mountain value chains were also presented.

The event gathered around 70 attendees from different backgrounds (research, public authorities, advisors, business, producers, other EU-funded projects, etc.), representing over 25 countries. All the [presentations](#) and [recordings](#) of the webinar are available on the [event page](#). The [highlights report](#) is available on the website and in [Zenodo](#).

Fourth EU MAP webinar on “Towards a Policy Roadmap for vibrant mountain economies” (8 May 2024). MOVING held its [fourth EU MAP webinar](#) on *Towards a Policy Roadmap for vibrant mountain economies* on 8 May 2024. The event aimed to:

- Present the MOVING’s Strategic Options and Policy Roadmap;
- Provide an overview of the current discussions concerning post-2027 policy development, in particular the ones related to mountain and territorial development;
- Discuss how MOVING’s Strategic Options and Policy Roadmap can be supported within the post-2027 EU policies.

During the webinar, a presentation from the project coordinator provided an overview of the project’s achievements over the past four years. Following this, experts from the European Commission and European Parliament offered an overview of key policies for mountain areas and their potential evolutions in the future (LTVRA and Cohesion Policy). Additionally, MOVING’s 30 Strategic Options for enhancing mountain sustainability and its Policy Roadmap were presented. The Policy Roadmap was further commented on in a final round table discussion, which focused on how future policies should support Europe’s mountains.

The event gathered 81 attendees from different backgrounds (research, public authorities, advisors, business, producers, other EU-funded projects, etc.), representing over 24 countries. All the [presentations](#) and [recordings](#) of the webinar are available on the [event page](#). The [highlights report](#) is available on the website and in [Zenodo](#).

Event: “The new legal framework for EU Quality Products: opportunities and challenges for mountain and GI products” (10 April 2024)

Within the framework of the Horizon 2020 MOVING project, AREPO, Euromontana and oriGIn EU hosted a conference on 10 April 2024 at the Committee of the Regions in Brussels, Belgium. The event brought together EU Institutions, regional governments, producers of mountain and GI products, and agri-food sector stakeholders to explore the implications of the new regulation and how to ensure the unique characteristics of these products are preserved within the next Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) and other EU legislation.

A session was devoted to the implementation of the Optional Quality Term ‘Mountain Product’, the most recent among EU quality schemes. AREPO, together with Highclere Consulting and

Euromontana, conducted a survey to report on the state of the art of the implementation of the OQT Mountain Product across the EU. The main results and policy recommendations were presented during the conference to discuss how to strengthen this OQT and increase its added value for the ecological resilience, attractiveness, and socio-economic development of mountain areas. All the [presentations](#) and [recordings](#) of the conference are available on the [event page](#). The [report](#) on the *Analysis of the Implementation of the EU Optional Quality Term “Mountain Product”* is available on the website and in [Zenodo](#).

Other additional EU MAP activities are compiled in the following table:

Table 6. EU MAP additional activities

Activity	Description	Timing
Contributions to open consultations and other processes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contribution to the stakeholder hearing and Opinion on Targets and tools for a Smart Rural Europe (Srsen, COR-2022-04320) • Contribution to the EU public consultation on agri-food system transition • Contribution and presentation during the stakeholder hearing on the Opinion of the European Economic and Social Committee (EESC) “Towards a greater involvement of Member States, Regions and Civil Society actors in the implementation of the Long-Term Vision for the EU’s Rural Areas (LTVRA) (Decoster, NAT/914-EESC-2023), - “How to exploit the full potential of cohesion policy to tackle demographic change” (García, COTER-VII/043) • Contribution to the Committee of the Regions (CoR) Opinion The Future of the Common Agricultural Policy (Gomes-Galbecki, CoR-2023-05512) • Contribution to CoR Opinion on Supporting SMEs in regional value chains – fostering the proximity economy (COR-2024-02105N) • Evidence from the MOVING policy outputs was included in the drafting of two key CoR opinions “EU budget and place-based policies: proposals for new design and delivery mechanisms in the MFF post-2027” (Maupertuis, in preparation) and “Enhancing Cohesion Policy support for regions with geographic and demographic handicaps (art 174 TFEU)” (Maupertuis, CoR-2022-02959) as AEIDL experts acted as technical draftsman of both opinions. 	Mid 2023- August 2024
Campaigns	<p>Women move Europe’s mountains, a booklet to celebrate women. To celebrate the International Mountain Day on 11 December 2022, and following the year’s theme, MOVING, together with Euromontana, published a booklet (77 downloads) titled “Women move Europe’s mountains” (available in English, French and Spanish). It is a compilation of 13 testimonies from women who either live in mountain areas of Europe or work to make them more sustainable and future focused. A blog article (183 views) was produced to promote it on social media:</p>	December 2022

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Twitter: 2 105 impressions • Facebook: 535 impressions • Instagram: 463 impressions • LinkedIn: Analytics not available after a year 	
Infographics	https://www.moving-h2020.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/12/MOVING_InternationalMountainDay.pdf MOVING European Multi-Actor Platform (EU MAP)	January 2023
Blog articles and news item	See all blog articles here and news item here . Also see section 4.2 MOVING communication products of this report.	Throughout years 3 and 4

Source: MOVING H2020

Activity in the Virtual Research Environment in relation to the EU MAP

For the functioning of the EU MAP, relationships between the members need to be established by encouraging them to exchange knowledge and learn from each other. For that, a dedicated Virtual Research Environment (VRE) is available on the MOVING Gateway starting from November 2021.

Figure 23. MOVING EU MAP VRE Home

Source: MOVING H2020

Figure 24 (MOVING EU MAP VRE users from M25 to M48) reveals a consistent growth in engagement from July 2022 to June 2024. Starting with 51 users in July 2022, the platform saw a steady increase, with a notable rise in April 2023. By June 2024, the number of users peaked at 94.

Figure 24. MOVING EU MAP VRE users from M25 to M48

Source: MOVING H2020

This steady growth reflects the platform's success in attracting and retaining stakeholders interested in resilience to climate change of mountain value chains. On average, the platform engaged approximately 69 users per month over the two-year period, demonstrating its expanding influence and the growing interest in its offerings. The user base stabilizes at around 92-94 users from January 2024, indicating a strong and sustained community engagement.

4.1.4. Social media

MOVING’s social media accounts aim to increase awareness among users, while encouraging them to check and read the project’s outputs. Each social media channel is intended to reach a specific audience, and the messages are adapted accordingly. The content shared on each platform includes different types of outputs, usually directing traffic to the MOVING website. Social media acts as an accelerator of the discussion, triggering a snowball effect and enabling the project to reach beyond its ‘usual suspects’ audience.

Twitter

Created in September 2020 for the project’s Kick-off Meeting, the MOVING Twitter account (@MOVINGH2020) serves as the main corporate account for the project, operating in English and managed by the WP1 Lead, AEIDL. During the period analysed, the project’s Twitter account has shared **410 posts**, plus several shares of content from third-party organisations.

Figure 25 shows the distribution of MOVING tweets by topic according to the categories described in Annex II. Categories to classify MOVING social media post.

Figure 25. MOVING Twitter posts by topic

Source: Own calculation through Twitter Insights, consulted on 5 August 2024

Out of the 410 tweets published by MOVING in Years 3 and 4, the majority (around 73%) cover topics related to MOVING, while the remaining tweets feature content from third parties. The significant share of project-related tweets is due to the numerous project results and events that MOVING has hosted. Additionally, live tweeting was conducted for each of the project events.

Regarding the format, tweets are usually accompanied by media assets to catch the users' attention. This can include pictures, GIFs, links or videos. By the end of the period analysed, the MOVING twitter account had **966 followers** (M48 target: 1 000 followers). Figure 26 shows a clear increasing tendency in Twitter followers, as illustrated by the green bars. The orange line in the same figure shows the number of impressions reached by the Twitter posts each month.

Figure 26. Evolution of the No followers and impressions on MOVING's Twitter account

Source: Own calculations based on Twitter Analytics data consulted on 5 August 2024

To better engage local audiences, the project coordinator, UCO, created and managed the Twitter account @H2020Moving_UCO. This account specifically targets Spanish-speaking audiences and covers the three Reference Regions in Spain, ensuring more effective communication and engagement with the local community. Additionally, partner organisations with Twitter accounts also echoed MOVING activities. For instance, AREPO, the James Hutton Institute, Highclere Consulting, and the University of Pisa shared and promoted the project's updates.

Facebook

During the period analysed, the project's Facebook page has shared **241 posts**, plus several shares of content from third-party organisations. Figure 27 shows the type of content published on the MOVING Facebook page according to the categories included in Annex II. Categories to classify MOVING social media post.

Figure 27. Distribution of MOVING posts in Facebook by category of content

Source: Meta Business Suite data consulted on 2 August 2024

More than half of the posts (67%) cover topics strictly related to MOVING, while the remaining 33% consists of content produced by third parties. This third-party content includes webinars organised by European stakeholders, updates on other Horizon 2020 projects, relevant documents published by European Institutions, and posts related to International Days. As most relevant MOVING results were released in Years 3 and 4, it's important to note that MOVING's communication strategy has prioritised the dissemination of its own progress.

The posts published on the Facebook page include media to attract the users' attention, such as links, pictures or videos. Figure 28 shows the distribution of MOVING posts according to the type of media included with the posts. Facebook's algorithm often penalises posts that include external links. That is why posts that include images or video have a higher reach (impressions) than those that only include a link as a call to action (Figure 29).

Figure 28. Posts of Facebook page per content type

Source: Meta Business Suite, consulted on 2 August 2024

Figure 29. Impressions of Facebook posts per content type

Source: Meta Business Suite, consulted on 2 August 2024

By the end of the period analysed, the Facebook page had **353 followers** and 285 likes (M48 target: 300 followers). The new developments of Facebook pages indicate that ‘followers’ is a better number to track as these are users who may see the page’s updates and posts in their news feed. Users who liked the page automatically followed it as well, but with the new Facebook Pages Experience, those same users can unfollow the page and thus not see the page’s updates and posts in their newsfeed.

Figure 30 shows the activity of new Facebook followers over Year 3 and 4. Overall, the graph suggests that while the page had steady growth in new followers over the observed period, there were certain days that saw significantly higher engagement leading to a spike in new followers.

Figure 30. Activity of new Facebook followers

Source: Meta Business Suite, consulted on 2 August 2024

Figure 31 represents the number of visits to the MOVING Facebook page over the analysed period. It indicates a consistent daily visit count with occasional peaks.

Figure 31. Number of visits to the Facebook page

Source: Meta Business Suite, consulted on 2 August 2024

Table 7, on the other hand, shows the country of origin of the Facebook followers during Years 3 and 4. The Top10 countries correspond to a country where MOVING has established at least one Multi-Actor Platform.

Table 7. Country of origin of MOVING Facebook followers

No	Country	Share
1	Italy	16,7%
2	Spain	11,9%
3	Greece	9,3%
4	Turkey	7,6%
5	Portugal	6,8%
6	France	6,5%
7	Romania	6,2%
8	Switzerland	4%
9	Serbia	3,4%
10	Hungary	2,8%

Source: Meta Business Suite, consulted on 2 August 2024

In order to increase the outreach of the project, MOVING has joined different groups related to rural development, youth, research and innovation, and Horizon 2020 projects. At the moment, the project is part of the following Facebook groups:

- Friends of ERP - European Rural Parliament. Created on 16 November 2016, it has now 638 members. The topics addressed by the group are about rural development, youth, digitalisation, climate change, smart villages, value chains, mountains and more.
- Horizon 2020, Framework Programme for Research and Innovation. Created on 8 July 2013, it has now 6310 members. The group posts about innovation, research, Horizon 2020, events, training, open calls, etc.

LinkedIn

During Years 3 and 4, the MOVING company page on LinkedIn ([MOVING - Mountain Valorisation through Interconnectedness and Green Growth](#)) has shared **388 posts**, plus several shares from third parties, accumulating a total of **76 907 impressions**. Figure 29 shows the type of contents published on the MOVING LinkedIn page according to the categories included in Annex II. By the time of analysis, MOVING’s LinkedIn company page had **995 followers** (M48 target: 800).

Figure 32. Posts of LinkedIn page per content type

Source: LinkedIn Analytics, consulted on 2 August 2024

As with Facebook, MOVING's communication strategy has prioritised disseminating its own progress. Consequently, more than half of the posts (65%) cover topics strictly related to MOVING, while the remaining 35% consists of content produced by third parties.

MOVING has also joined different groups related to rural development, sustainability and Horizon 2020 projects to bring the updates and results of the project to more people. At the moment, is part of the group Sustainable Agriculture & Rural Development.

The group was created in October 2012 and now has 74 935 members. Its aim is to create an international professional network favourable for exchanging information, knowledge, interaction (synergy) and capacity building on various aspects of rural development linked to MOVING interest: economic development, innovations in value chains (such as olive oil), bioeconomy, farmer organisations, land-use planning, food systems or climate change.

Instagram

By the end of the period analysed, MOVING’s Instagram account had earned **328 followers (M48 target: 300)**, through 152 posts and 166 stories. Figure 33 shows the type of contents published on Instagram according to the categories included in Annex II. Categories to classify MOVING social media post. Due to the steady growth of the audience on Instagram, the strategy has been to publish similar content to other channels to keep the audience informed, always prioritising updates about MOVING and its regions.

Figure 33. Posts of Instagram page per content type

Source: Meta Business Suite, consulted on 2 August 2024

Table 8 shows the top 5 countries of origin of MOVING’s Instagram followers. All five of them correspond to countries where the project has established at least one Multi-Actor Platform.

Table 8. Country of origin of MOVING Instagram followers

No	Country	Share
1	Spain	20,4%
2	Italy	18,9%
3	Turkey	6.1%

4	France	5,2%
5	Switzerland	4,9%

Source: Meta Business Suite, consulted on 2 August 2024

Youtube

Launched in March 2021, the MOVING YouTube account (@[MOVINGH2020](#)) stores all the audio-visual material the project has produced. The channel currently hosts **101 videos** produced by the project publicly available.

By the end of M47, the channel counted with **4 896 views** plus 185 extra views (M48 target: 3 500) of videos that are currently unpublished or private because they have been updated or modified. See section 4.2.5 of this report for more details.

The total amount of views and the distribution over the period analysed are depicted in Figure 34.

Figure 34. Views of the MOVING YouTube Channel in Year 3 and 4.

Source: YouTube Studio analytics, consulted on 2 August 2024

The MOVING videos hosted in YouTube have been widely promoted through social media and other means. Table 9 shows the Top5 most viewed videos and their average duration per session.

Table 9. Figure 33. Top 5 most viewed MOVING videos on YouTube

Video name	Total views	Views in Year 3 and 4	Average view duration
<u>MOVING community: working together for the future of mountain value chains</u>	966	464	0:53
<u>MOVING meeting in Switzerland At what stage is the project now?</u>	185	185	1:19
<u>20. Vulnerability and resilience of mountain grain Swiss Alps Region (CH)</u>	176	176	1:15

MOVING Workshop Unlocking the Power of Mountain Value Chains	176	176	2:24
MOVING Know the 23 Mountains Reference Regions and its Value Chains	220	172	0:50

Source: YouTube Studio analytics, consulted on 2 August 2024

The MOVING YouTube channel has **62 subscribers**. Figure 35 illustrates the performance in the number of impressions (**60 126**) over the analysed period.

Figure 35. Impressions in the MOVING YouTube channel in Years 3 and 4

Source: YouTube Studio analytics, consulted on 2 August 2024

As shown in the figure, there are several peaks in impressions. Notable peaks occurred around January and February 2023, coinciding with the upload of the MOVING Digital Stories. Additional peaks in October 2023, as well as in April and May 2024, align with the uploads of the sessions from the 3rd MOVING EU MAP webinar, the GIs event, and the 4th EU MAP webinar, respectively.

4.1.5. Newsletter

The MOVING newsletter aims to communicate the developments of the project, as well as relevant information about other Horizon projects, European institutions or international organisations working on mountain value chains that may be interesting to the subscribers.

Two newsletters are sent out **every year**, usually in June and December. The date of publishing is kept flexible, so it can be adapted to specific events or publications that might be of special relevance to the MOVING audience. In that case, newsletters may be earlier or later than the estimated date of publication. The decision is taken by AEIDL and the Project Coordinator.

The MOVING newsletter is managed by using Mailchimp, sent to a distribution list, shared through social media channels and then published on the dedicated webpage. Table 10 shows an overview of the MOVING newsletters published in Years 3 and 4 of the project. The 'opening rate' refers to the percentage of people subscribed to the mailing list that effectively open the

newsletter. The ‘click rate’ refers to the percentage of hyperlinks included in the newsletter that were open by at least one reader.

Mailchimp tracks the interaction that subscribers have with the newsletter on the original email sent out by the platform, but the interaction achieved through other channels, such as social media, email forwards, or the MOVING website, cannot be measured. Therefore, the data shown in Table 10 should be understood as an underestimation of the actual data.

Table 10. Overview of MOVING newsletters in Years 3 and 4

No.	Edition	Opening rate	Click rate	No. of subscribers
4	December 2022 edition	42,7%	14,1%	258
5	June 2023 edition	34,1%	11,7%	306
6	December 2023 edition	35%	10%	331
7	April 2024 edition	32,6%	10,1%	333
8	September 2024 edition ⁶	-	-	-

Source: Mailchimp, consulted on 2 August 2024

By the end of the period analysed, the newsletter counts with **336 subscribers** (target: 350). Figure 36 and Figure 37 show a categorisation of the subscribers by country and category of stakeholder. Most MOVING newsletter subscribers are from one of the countries where MOVING has a partner such as Italy, Spain, Greece, France, and Belgium (see Figure 36). The majority belong to research institutes (35%), with significant representation from public authorities (13%), stakeholder organisations (5%), and NGOs (8%).

It is important to note that data is unavailable for one-third of the subscribers, as no information was provided on their profile (N/A).

⁶ By the time the newsletter is sent, this deliverable will have been submitted, which is why no analytics are available for this last edition.

Figure 36. MOVING newsletter subscribers sorted by country

Source: Mailchimp, consulted on 2 August 2024

Figure 37. MOVING newsletter subscribers by category of stakeholders

Source: Mailchimp, consulted on 2 August 2024

4.1.6. MOVING App

The 'MOVING MOUNTAINS' App has been designed to foster engagement with mountain region resilience among both local residents and visitors. This application facilitates the identification and sharing of information, playing a vital role in connecting people with mountains.

A detailed description of the work, including all implementation decisions, achievements, and deviations, has been reported in a living document called D1.2 MOVING Mountains App, submitted in December 2022 (M28). In January 2023, the first version of the MOVING Mountains app was released to a selected community of alpha testers, accompanied by a detailed installation manual.

In February and March 2023, Nubisware S.r.L. collected feedback from alpha users of the MOVING Mountains app and used it to prepare a beta version of the mobile application. This beta version was released to a wider audience, including MOVING partners and stakeholders, in April 2023. It integrates the improvements suggested during the first testing phase and enhances some core functionalities.

As of March 2024, the app is available for download on the Google Play Store, designed to enhance the experience for Android mobile device users. Nubisware is working to develop a version for iOS users.

During this period, there have been a minimum estimated app total of 70 downloads of the MOVING Mountains app, according to UCO technical services, as some have been done from VRE, the two most important App stores and the website, where number of downloads is not provided. The app has only recently been widely available hence it is expected the target to be reached during 2024.

4.2. MOVING communication and dissemination products

MOVING has produced a wide range of communication and dissemination materials about its results. Communication products were designed to provide an overview/summary of the key messages across different project's results to obviate to lengthy deliverables. As such, they are understood as complementary to more detailed information which is provided into the project's deliverables. The MOVING communication products have different layouts and language styles according to the target audience it is meant to reach.

By the means of an assessment survey launched in January 2024, the Communication Task Force members were asked to rate the usefulness of different types of content shared with MOVING (Figure 38). Information related to MOVING research findings and deliverables received the highest rating, with 68.18% of responses, followed by webinars and events at 63.64%, and videos at 50%. Lower usefulness was reported for MOVING Story Maps, with 22.73% of responses, and the MOVING podcast, with 27.27% of responses.

Figure 38. Usefulness of the MOVING content for partners

Source: MOVING H2020

4.2.1. Visual identity of the project

By using a unique visual identity throughout the consortium and all our products, **consistency** and a **strong brand recognition** is ensured in MOVING communications and dissemination. Templates for different types of documents (e.g. agenda, concept note, deliverable, PPT) were developed and shared with the Consortium. Templates are important to give a uniform image of the project and establish a visual language to indicate the information presented derives from the MOVING project. The MOVING visual identity complies with the visual guidelines of the European Commission.

The main elements of the visual identity package of MOVING comprise:

1. Logo, in several applications and formats (vertical and horizontal applications, coloured and black and white versions);
2. Graphic Charter, including the corporate colours and typographies to be used in the MOVING communication materials;

3. Template package, including templates for presentations, deliverables, agenda, working documents, and event communications. All of these templates include the EU logo and disclaimer, and are updated when needed (e.g. a partner changes their visual identity).
4. The project roll-ups have been designed in English and translated into three languages.

All of these elements are available in the project VRE for partners to use.

During the period analysed, the template for the newsletter was updated to make it more attractive and engaging. The template for Deliverables was also updated (M34) to include a "Status" field indicating whether a deliverable is "submitted" (to the European Commission) or "approved" (by the European Commission).

4.2.2. News

The website's [news section](#) is key to keeping interested parties up to date, generating traffic to the site and retaining the audience. The information provided is on the results of the project, on the latest news in rural policy, and on events that MOVING has attended or organised. Overall, MOVING has published a total of **136 news** (76 news in Years 3 and 4) (some of them under more than one category), which are filtered as follows:

Table 11. Number of news items

Category	News Years 3 and 4	Total number of news (from Year 1 to 4)	Topics
MOVING	42	78	Mountains, value chains, multi-actor platform, vulnerability, reference region, climate change, meeting, mountain products, policy brief, youth, foresight, agriculture.
EU institutions	17	28	Rural development, land abandonment, climate change, agriculture, Cohesion Policy, climate action, forest, biodiversity, youth, geographical indications.
European stakeholders	10	18	Geographical indications, mountain products, innovation, youth, climate action, good practices, value chains, climate change, forest, mountains, Cohesion Policy.
International organisations	5	11	Mountains, sustainability, mountain products, climate change.
H2020 projects	1	4	Rural development, sustainability, value chains, climate action.

Source: MOVING H2020

4.2.3. Blogs

Overall, **75 blog posts** have been published, with 25 written by European stakeholders and 50 by MOVING partners. Specifically, in Years 3 and 4, 15 blog articles were contributed by European stakeholders, and 37 were authored by MOVING partners.

Most popular blog posts throughout the MOVING project are⁷:

- [The revision of the EU Geographical Indications system](#) (326 views)
- [The presence of protected natural sites in MOVING’s Reference Regions](#) (206 views)
- [Women move Europe’s mountains, a booklet to celebrate women](#) (186 views)
- [The importance of women in the sustainability of mountain areas](#) (160 views)
- [Innovative and sustainable tourism in mountains regions](#) (113 views)

The MOVING blog posts aim to explain the project’s progress, disseminate results, share partners’ knowledge on project-related matters and stimulate innovation in mountain value chains.

For instance, to explain the Participatory multi-level foresight exercise and the development of the Repertoire of Strategic Options, two blog articles were prepared ([“Exploring the future of mountain regions: Insights from participatory foresight”](#) and [“From archetypes, Strategic Options and policy needs for mountains in 2050”](#)), detailing the methodology, findings, and future implications.

Blog posts from other institutions, organisations, and projects serve as a valuable vehicle to facilitate the formation of alliances, knowledge exchange, and engagement with the main actors and stakeholders of MOVING’s Community of Practice. For example, MOVING has developed various blog posts and interviews with experts from the University of Milan (UNIMONT), Euromontana, MountResilience project, Mountain Research and Development, University of Göttingen, SHERPA project, and Interreg POCTEFA, among others.

Table 12. Blogs post from year 3 to year 4

Blog articles/posts	Publishing date
Empowering Sustainable Mountain Development through Local Bottom-up Initiatives	July 2024
Exploring sustainable tourism practices: Highlights from MOVING’s cross-country visit to Romania	June 2024
Engaging with young people throughout MOVING	May 2024
From archetypes, Strategic Options and policy needs for mountains in 2050	April 2024
Exploring the future of mountain regions: Insights from participatory foresight	March 2024

⁷ Consulted on 2 August 2024

<u>Revitalising Crete through the carob flour value chain: A community of practice approach</u>	March 2024
<u>The EU Commission launches Communities for Climate: An initiative to support local citizens' actions to respond to climate change</u>	February 2024
<u>Enhancing Mountain Products: Insights from the TOP-Value EU Interreg Project</u>	February 2024
<u>Skills for the future of mountain value chains in Europe</u>	December 2023
<u>Were mountains the big absent at COP28?</u>	December 2023
<u>MountResilience: Accelerating transformative climate change adaptation for higher resilience in European mountain regions</u>	November 2023
<u>New EU system on geographical indications for craft and industrial products</u>	October 2023
<u>Shaping the future of Rural and Mountain policies: Insights from Sigüenza High-Level Policy Forum</u>	October 2023
<u>The EIDER project: Empowering rural development through education</u>	September 2023
<u>A strategy for mountain olive groves</u>	August 2023
<u>Diversity, people and governance, some of the key messages in the last 2023 EU AgriResearch Conference</u>	August 2023
<u>Why we need social innovations in mountain regions, and how to make them happen</u>	August 2023
<u>Building resilience in fragile mountain environments through value chain analysis</u>	August 2023
<u>Development of the Swiss food system: a perspective from 2050</u>	June 2023
<u>FAO publications towards sustainable GIs</u>	June 2023
<u>The cost of non-rurality: towards an assessment?</u>	June 2023
<u>A bright future for the Swiss Alps – Not at all?</u>	May 2023
<u>The role of carob flour in circular economy in Crete</u>	May 2023
<u>The presence of protected natural sites in MOVING's Reference Regions</u>	April 2023
<u>Is global warming irreversible? IPCC report warns us</u>	April 2023
<u>Mountain wildflower honey: an endangered "portrait" of mountain grasslands</u>	March 2023
<u>SHERPA's recommendations for resilient value chains</u>	March 2023
<u>Promising results to face the last stretch of the MOVING project</u>	February 2023
<u>What do professionals in the mountain sector think about MOVING?</u>	February 2023
<u>Harnessing talents for vibrant mountain areas</u>	January 2023
<u>Alternative future for mountains: How to get there?</u>	January 2023

<u>Discovering the singularity of high mountain products: an interview with Toni Massanés</u>	December 2022
<u>Youth's vision on the sustainable development of the Northern Apennines</u>	December 2022
<u>Women move Europe's mountains, a booklet to celebrate women</u>	December 2022
<u>Smart mountains thrive to be resilient, say stakeholders at XII European Mountain Convention</u>	December 2022
<u>Remote territories shall be considered by EU policies, reaffirms the EU Committee of the Regions</u>	December 2022
<u>New report for MEPs finds the need for more science to policy interfaces are needed in CAP negotiations</u>	December 2022
<u>The United Nations reports on sustainable mountain development</u>	November 2022
<u>What do professionals in the agricultural sector think about MOVING?</u>	November 2022
<u>A possible future for youth in the Sierra Morena Reference Region</u>	November 2022
<u>Recovering native varieties, the commitment of the Spanish Pyrenees wine value chain</u>	October 2022
<u>MOVING partners meet for the first time!</u>	October 2022
<u>Pessimism, the feeling of youth towards the carob flour value chain in Crete</u>	October 2022
<u>The EU CAP Network, the platform where MOVING contributions and the new CAP objectives can meet</u>	October 2022
<u>Evaluating Geographical Indications – Guide to tailor evaluation for the development and improvement of Geographical Indication</u>	October 2022
<u>Montana174 Conference highlights the challenges of Cohesion Policy in mountain areas</u>	September 2022
<u>Farm certification schemes for sustainable agriculture: specifications for origin and quality of the final products</u>	September 2022
<u>Youth for mountain sustainability: making their voice heard in decision-making processes</u>	August 2022
<u>Protected Designations of Origin and correlations with social-ecological landscape values</u>	August 2022
<u>MOVING contributed to the public consultation on Sustainable EU food system</u>	July 2022
<u>The future of young people in Crete: sustainable development and viable agri-value chains</u>	July 2022
<u>Appraisal on vulnerability and performance of rural tourism value chain in Maleshevski mountains</u>	July 2022

Source: MOVING H2020

By the end of the project, we plan to include several blog articles from external sources, particularly from the MountResilience, MARGISTAR, and GI-SMART projects, as well as from the [Rural Pact's Community on Mountains](#), which is currently available on the website. These articles will highlight how the MOVING community can engage with these initiatives in the future. Additionally, we anticipate blog articles about the final outcomes of the project, written by members of the consortium.

4.2.4. Policy Briefs

In Years 3 and 4, MOVING has published two sets of [Policy Briefs](#) (March 2024 and July 2024, respectively). The [first set](#) of these briefs, focused on the MOVING clusters, were developed based on the information gathered during the WP5 activities, specifically task 5.3 “Comparative assessment report on Mountain Value Chains”. These briefs include an introduction to the MOVING project and its activities, a synthesis of the specific cluster being referred to, the challenges addressed, policy recommendations, and the expected impact on cluster objectives.

The [second set](#) of these briefs, focused on policy issues relevant for the 23 value chains, were developed based on the information gathered during all the activities carried out throughout the project's lifetime, summarising the knowledge and experiences collected and reflecting on policies analysed in the VCs and the foresight exercises. These Policy Briefs are available in English and the native language of the country referred to.

During this period, a total of **261 Policy Brief downloads** were recorded. The most downloaded documents were⁸:

- [Central Apennines Policy Brief](#) - 33 downloads
- [D2.2 Initial Set of Policy Briefs](#) - 26 downloads
- [Swiss Alps Policy Brief](#) - 21 downloads

It is important to note that downloads for Years 1 and 2 were not considered, which is why the numbers appear relatively low. Additionally, at the time the analysis was conducted, the latest set of Policy Briefs had not yet been promoted on social media, so these numbers are expected to increase by the end of the project.

4.2.5. Practice Abstracts

In Years 3 and 4, MOVING has made available on the website two sets of [Practice Abstracts](#) (November 2022 and August 2023, respectively). The [first set](#) of Practice Abstracts, under WP1, comprised a total of 31 documents, provides key results and outcomes of specific tasks that have been carried out so far in MOVING; and main practical recommendation(s) to enable the practitioners make use of the results.

⁸ Consulted on 2 August 2024.

The [second set](#) of Practice Abstracts, under WP4, was composed of 31 Practice Abstracts summarising the key results and outcomes of tasks T4.3 – T4.5 and other tasks that have been carried out so far in MOVING.

The third set of Practice Abstracts, foreseen for M48, will be uploaded to the MOVING's Library and to the Practice Abstracts subsection before the project's closure. Overall, 120 Practice Abstracts will be produced and published by the end of the project.

In addition to submitting the Practice Abstracts in the EIP common format, they were also published in a leaflet layout. A subsection was created in August 2023 on the MOVING website to host these materials, under the webpage on "Publications". PAs are classified according to the 23 Reference Regions, and Other practices, which provides practical examples on the different activities carried out by MOVING.

After promoting the different sets through social media campaigns, the total number of visits to this specific page reached 372, with 224 unique users. A total of **659 Practice Abstracts downloads** were recorded during the analysed period. The most downloaded documents were⁹:

- [D1.8 Practice Abstracts \(1st batch\)](#) - 74 downloads
- [D4.7 Regional Practice Abstracts](#) (second batch) - 39 downloads
- [Speyside Malt Whisky](#) Practice Abstract (First set) - 31 downloads

It is worth noting that among the individual Practice Abstracts, the most downloaded one is from the UK-Scotland. This is likely because language is not a barrier in this case.

4.2.6. Podcast

Launched in October 2023, the [MOVING podcast "Conversations on Sustainable Mountains"](#), aims to summarise and present the research results from the MOVING project over the past four years. The purpose is to raise awareness about the project, its ongoing and forthcoming activities and results, and to give visibility to MOVING experts from the Consortium and Reference Regions.

The project has published a [teaser](#) and the five episodes planned:

- [Episode 1](#) - Change and vulnerability in mountains
- [Episode 2](#) - Exploring the diversity of Europe's mountains
- [Episode 3](#) - Revitalising mountain economies
- [Episode 4](#) - Foresight in action for mountain futures
- [Episode 5](#) - Aligning policies to mountain needs

Additionally, benefitting from the fact that both the host and the interviewee were Spanish, a [special edition](#) of the final episode was produced in both Spanish and English versions. This aimed to more widely disseminate the project in that particular language and national context.

⁹ Consulted on 2 August 2024.

MOVING’s podcast has **30 followers** in Spotify, and **81 plays**. Figure 39 illustrates the number of plays of the teaser and podcast episodes since it was launched. The figure shows several peaks, typically occurring when an episode was published or promoted on the project's social media channels.

Figure 39. Plays of the MOVING podcast episodes.

Source: Spotify for Podcasters Analytics, consulted on 2 August 2024

Table 13 shows the top 10 countries of origin of MOVING’s podcast listeners. Six out of ten of them correspond to countries where the project has established at least one Multi-Actor Platform.

Table 13. Country of origin of MOVING podcast listeners.

No	Country	Share
1	Spain	17%
2	Belgium	15%
3	Switzerland	13%
4	Italy	11%
5	France	9%
6	Portugal	6%
7	United States	5%
8	Norway	5%
9	United Kingdom	4%
10	Denmark	3%

Source : Spotify for Podcasters Analytics, consulted on 2 August 2024

The podcast was also hosted on the MOVING YouTube channel, where it received **91 views**. Overall, the podcast has accumulated **172 views/plays** as illustrated in Table 14.

Table 14. MOVING podcast episode rankings by platform

Episode	Plays in Spotify	Views in YouTube	Total
Teaser	9	21	30
EP1	29	34	63
EP2	19	16	35
EP3	20	9	29
EP4	4	4	8
EP5	0	7	7
Spanish episode	2	-	2

Source : Spotify for Podcasters Analytics and YouTube analytics, consulted on 2 August 2024

The MOVING podcast was distributed via social media and included in the project's newsletters, with support from AEIDL's and partners' social media and newsletter platforms. Additionally, AEIDL prepared a [news item](#) and, after some time following the release, a [press release](#) to further promote the podcast.

The podcast's distribution strategy also included targeted outreach to key organisations, such as Euromontana, the Mountain Partnership, Mountain Research Initiative, Interreg Alpine Space, and the European Rural Pact Support Office, encouraging them to reshare the content.

4.2.7. Videos

So far, in Years 3 and 4, **80 videos** have been produced by MOVING and uploaded to the project's [YouTube channel](#). The videos are categorised into 11 playlists (community, results, digital stories, EU MAP webinars (3), events, about MOVING, podcast, interviews, and partners) totalling 3851 views¹⁰.

¹⁰ Consulted on 2 August 2024.

Table 15. MOVING videos and playlists in years 3 and 4

Playlist	Videos
Community	The video “Unlocking the power of mountain value chains” showcases the main highlights of the MOVING Cluster Workshop, featuring testimonials from partners and local actors from the 23 Reference Regions. It has 176 views.
Project’s Results	<p>Assessing the vulnerability of mountain regions with MOVING's visual tools. This video promotes the set of visual tools produced under WP3, which focus on challenges faced by mountain communities and ecosystems. It has a total of 12 views.</p> <p>MOVING's Repertoire of Strategic Options for the future of mountain communities. This video introduces the results of the foresight exercises and presents the concept of Strategic Plans. It has a total of 14 views.</p> <p>A video on the Policy Roadmap is planned for release at the end of the project to promote this key result.</p>
Digital Stories	The MOVING Digital Stories is a package of 23 short videos that provide an overview of the vulnerability of mountain value chains in European and neighbourhood countries. It has a total of 2129 views.
2nd EU MAP webinar	The nine videos of the second EU MAP webinar “European Quality Schemes: the added value for mountain value chains” have a total of 198 views.
3rd EU MAP webinar	The nine videos of the third EU MAP webinar “Protected natural sites: A constraint or an opportunity for mountain value chains?” have a total of 133 views.
4th EU MAP webinar	The six videos of the fourth EU MAP webinar “Towards a Policy Roadmap for vibrant mountain economies” have a total of 130 views.
Conference on GIs	The 14 videos of the MOVING conference “The new legal framework for EU Quality Products: opportunities and challenges for mountain and GI products” have a total of 170 views.
About MOVING	The video featuring the project coordinator is an interview recorded during the first physical meeting of the MOVING partners. It showcases the project’s progress and outlines the next steps. The video includes subtitles and has been translated into seven languages. It has a total of 353 views.
Podcast	The five episodes of the MOVING podcast plus the teaser have a total of 91 views.
Interviews	<p>What are the next steps of MOVING?. This video summarises the next steps of MOVING in its final phase. It has 41 views.</p> <p>Conceptual framework for mountain development. This video sheds light on the essential components necessary for understanding mountain ecosystems and the</p>

	significance of the MOVING Conceptual Analytical Framework in enhancing policies and research for mountain development. It has 56 views.
Partners	<p>A total of five videos have been facilitated by partners from different RRs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sierra Morena (coordinated by University of Cordoba): (i) MOVING Scientific Conference in Cordoba (12 views); (ii) How a livestock farmer works at Los Pedroches? The story of Marian Navas (168 views); and (iii) MOVING How a livestock farmer works at Los Pedroches? The story of Antonio Fernández (28 views). • Betic Systems (coordinated by ADEGUA): Workshop with youth on the future of mountain areas (79 views). • Eastern Alps, Maciço Noroeste and Spanish Pyrenees (coordinated by VINIDEA): Effects of climate change on the mountain wine value chain (61 views).

Source: MOVING H2020

4.2.8. Other products

MOVING has produced several other communication materials, available in the website's [Library](#). In Years 3 and 4, the project has published six press releases:

- [MOVING workshop in Hungary](#) (10 November 2023)
- [MOVING European Foresight Workshop](#) (12 January 2024)
- [MOVING podcast: Conversations on Sustainable Mountains](#) (4 March 2024)
- [MOVING Scientific Conference in Cordoba](#) (21 March 2024)
- [GIs and mountain products take centre stage in Brussels](#) (11 April 2024)
- [MOVING Final Conference charts future for mountain areas in post-2027 EU priorities](#) (19 June 2024)
- MOVING Policy Roadmap (planned for September 2024 to promote this key outcome of the project)

MOVING has also produced seven infographics:

- [MOVING European Multi-Actor Platform](#) (EU MAP) (January 2023).
- [MOVING Clusters](#) (April 2023) related to WP5 activities.
- [Value creation in mountains](#) (October 2023) related to WP4 results.
- [Mountain Value Chains: Our treasure](#) (October 2023) related to WP4 results.
- [Building Resilience to Overcome Vulnerability](#) (October 2023), related to D3.2 Land use systems vulnerability matrixes and vulnerability maps for the 23 reference regions.
- [Engaging youth in MOVING mountains](#) (May 2024), related to D1.5 Youth engagement report.
- [MOVING outcomes: a 4-year journey](#) (June 2024).

4.3. External channels for outreach

4.3.1. Partners' communication channels and activities

In addition to the MOVING channels, the consortium partners promote the project through their own communication and dissemination channels, as well as multiplying networks and organisations. Based on the MOVING survey results (see Annex I), the main channels used by partners were the “Workshops and events organised by my organisation” (22%), “Email” (19%), “Social Media accounts of my organisation” (19%), and “Website of my organisation” (13%).

In total, **212 actions** have been carried out by partners during Years 3 and 4 through their communication channels. Figure 40 showcases the main types of media used to carry out these communication activities, including personal social media channels, organisation’s social media channels, newsletters and websites.

Figure 40. Type of media used by MOVING partners to communicate through their communication channels

Source: MOVING H2020

Additionally, Figure 41 shows the area of influence of the partner’s communication activities. As can be observed, the majority of activities have an international and European influence (75%), followed by national-level activities (16%), local-level activities (8%), and regional-level activities (1%).

Figure 41. Area of influence of the MOVING partner's communication activities

Source: MOVING H2020

According to the internal communication and dissemination tool, during the final phase of the project, partners engaged in several dissemination activities, such as:

- Organising the event "The New Legal Framework for EU Quality Products: Opportunities and Challenges for Mountain and GI Products".
- Final presentation of MOVING project results for policy-makers in Serbia.
- Presentation of MOVING results organised by ADEGUA.
- Presentation of MOVING results by UCO to Sierra Morena and to the province of Cordoba.
- Final event to disseminate the project results in Greece.
- Final event on Dairy supply chain in Alto Molise.
- Organisation of a Summer School in Romania with local youth.
- Two regional country visits: one to the Southern Romanian Carpathians and another to Scotland (Cairngorms National Park) for partners and local actors.
- Shared draft policy brief with Scottish Government Food and Drink Analysts and also Scotch Whisky Association.

In some cases, efforts were made by partners to summarise the project results in their local language, making the findings more accessible to local stakeholders, as illustrated in Figure X below.

Figure 42. Example of the report elaborated by UCO to deliver all the project results to its MAP members.

MOVING has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 862739.

Los Mecanismos adaptativos, resultado de los factores de vulnerabilidad para Sierra Morena (la sequía, orientada hacia la sobreexplotación de los recursos (carga ganadera) y las plagas y las enfermedades) y analizados bajo los factores explícitos espaciales (las flujos y la densidad de cobertura arbórea), fueron a analizados como se muestra a continuación.

3.1. ¿Cómo se analizaron estos mecanismos adaptativos?
Mediante el cruce de su viabilidad y su capacidad de reducir la vulnerabilidad en valores ≥ 1.8 .

Cada uno de estos mecanismos adaptativos se analizó bajo el umbral de su capacidad media para reducir la vulnerabilidad, establecida en ≥ 1.8 , incluida su viabilidad media (de 1 a 3) en criterios económicos, técnicos, sociales y ambientales. El análisis de los mecanismos se muestra en la siguiente ilustración:

4.3.2. Link to other networks and projects

The project's website includes a [dedicated webpage for networking](#), including other H2020 projects and other projects, European Institutions and Agencies, European organisations and international organisations.

MOVING is part of the cluster of the **Rural Renaissance call** (RUR-01 and RUR-02) together with SHERPA, DESIRA, RURALIZATION and POLIRURAL. The cluster aims to foster collaboration and knowledge exchange between the projects, building on each other's activities, and boosting the communication and dissemination of outcomes, contributing to the future rural policies. Some of the activities realised within this Rural Cluster have led to MOVING articles and updates published in newsletters and websites of [SHERPA](#), [DESIRA](#) or [POLIRURAL](#).

In addition, MOVING was showcased at the DESIRA and SHERPA Final Conferences (respectively in April and June 2023). Though all projects of the cluster of the Rural Renaissance call ended by Q3 2023, MOVING continued its collaboration and communication synergies with EU-funded projects. In particular, its outputs and events were promoted via the **GRANULAR**,

MountResilience, SMARTERA, RUSTIK, BEATLES, RESIST, RURALITIES, CODECS and MARGISTAR communication channels.

Overall, **26 outputs and events** were shared by the Horizon projects mentioned above. Figure 43 showcases the main types of media used by the projects to carry out these communication activities. Half of these activities (50%) were conducted through the projects’ social media channels, followed by newsletters (42%) and website publications (8%).

Figure 43. Type of media used by Horizon projects

Source: MOVING H2020

MOVING also relies on the channels of several European and international organisations and networks, which act as multipliers and contribute to disseminating the project’s key messages and outputs. In particular, the MOVING results, news and events were shared through the **Rural Pact** and the **EU CAP network** respective newsletters and website. MOVING also participated to the EU CAP Network Expert Group on “**Competitive and Resilience Mountain Areas**” which took place on 7 March 2024. Similarly, results and relevant news from the Rural Pact, EU CAP network and related institutional channels (DG REGIO, DG AGRI) were shared through MOVING communication channels (e.g. website, social media). Upon completion of all deliverables, MOVING results will be shared results on the **Rural Pact Community Group on Mountains**, the **EU Farmbook** and the **Horizon Results Platform**.

Different content and posts on social media have been shared by organisations and institutions such as: [UNESCO Man and Biosphere](#), [EESC Agriculture Rural Development and Fisheries](#), [DG REGIO Regional & Urban Policy department of the EC](#), European Parliament [Intergroup RUMRA](#); the [European Network for Rural Development \(ENRD\)](#), [Euromontana](#), [FAO Mountain Partnership](#), [Mountain research Initiative](#), [Mountain Biodiversity](#), [EURAC Research](#), the [Centre](#)

for Mountain Studies at Perth College UHI, UniMont, Mountain Forum, Adaptation at Altitude, Europe Direct Pyrenees, as well as National Rural Networks specially from Spain, Portugal and Romania.

Figure 44 shows the main types of media used by the multiplier organisations mentioned above to share outcomes about MOVING. In total, **65 actions** were carried out by these organisations, with the main ones being newsletter appearances and blog posts, and social media posts.

Figure 44. Type of media used by multiplier organisations

Source: MOVING H2020

4.3.3. Participation in third party events

Partners have participated in several external events to present the project and its results to external audiences. According to the data reported in the internal tool for monitoring communication and dissemination activities, MOVING has been presented in 69 external events. These have been classified according to the categories used by the European Commission in the Funding and Tenders Portal. Figure 45 shows the type of events MOVING partners have participated in, while Figure 46 shows the area of influence of the events attended.

Figure 45. Type of events attended by MOVING partners communicating and disseminating results and findings of the project.

Source: MOVING H2020

Figure 46. Area of influence of the events attended by MOVING partners.

Source: MOVING H2020

Out of the total number of events, 8 were held online, while the rest (61) took place face-to-face. Regarding the type of participation, all events included an oral presentation or talk, a poster or abstract submission, or the distribution of brochures/flyers about the results and findings of the project.

4.3.4. Relation with press and media

Media are a great way to improve the visibility of MOVING. Partners are encouraged to try to publish via these channels to communicate to regional or national audiences about the project, its results and the Multi-Actor Platforms – as well as the funding received from the EC and the Horizon 2020 programme. In total, **281 actions** have been carried out by partners during years 3 and 4. The figures below showcase the main types of actions, and the level at which these actions have been coordinated (area of influence).

Figure 47. Distribution of actions by type of media

Source: MOVING H2020

Figure 48. Area of influence of the media actions undertaken by MOVING partners.

Source: MOVING H2020

Notable to mention the high number of ‘website’ category. About 57% of these refer to online information and news websites at national, regional and local levels. There has been a further increase in the project results in the last months of the project particularly ahead and during the final conference. Particular outreach was made to specialist and generalist media, including a press kit for the Final Conference.

Furthermore, the project appeared on several media outlets at regional and national levels, such as Gazzetta delle Valli (Italy), Cretalive News (Greece), Tribuna de Andalucía (Spain), Infowine (Italy), Europa Press (Spain), Parola (Hungary), and Mercacei (Spain).

These are a few examples of actions carried out by project partners in an effort to disseminate and raise awareness of MOVING through the various channels available to them.

- University of Córdoba, as coordinator of the project, and ADEGUA has established regular links with local and regional media channels, such as Diario de Córdoba, ABC Córdoba or Onda Cero.
- VINIDEA uses its magazine on viticulture and enology, Infowine, to disseminate information. The magazine offers content in six languages: Spanish, English, Italian, Portuguese, French, and German.
- The Region of Crete has good and established connections with local and regional media. Their [press releases](#) are usually picked up by many online news and blog websites, such as CRETALIVE NEWS, Flashnews, ΠΕΘΕΜΝΙΩΤΙΚΑ ΝΕΑ and ΚΡΗΤΙΚΗ ΕΠΙΘΕΩΡΗΣΗ.

4.5.1. Publications in scientific journals

During Years 3 and 4, MOVING outputs have been published in 10 peer-reviewed publications, including articles in scientific journals and book chapters. This marks a significant improvement from the previous report (D1.4), where no approved scientific publications were recorded.

The MOVING publications are published by the time this document was delivered are:

- Allali, T., Colabianchi, M., Moretti, M., & Brunori, G. (2024). Towards a new framework to assess agri-food value chains’ sustainability – The case of chestnut value chain. *Heliyon*, 10(7), e27836. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2024.e27836>
- Bartalesi, V., Coro, G., Lenzi, E., Pagano, P., & Pratelli, N. (2023). From unstructured texts to semantic story maps. *International Journal of Digital Earth*, 16(1), 234–250. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17538947.2023.2168774>
- Bartalesi, V., Coro, G., Lenzi, E., Pratelli, N., Pagano, P., Felici, F., Moretti, M., & Brunori, G. (2023). Using semantic story maps to describe a territory beyond its map. *Semantic Web*, 14(6), 1255–1272. <https://doi.org/10.3233/sw-233485>
- Delgado S. (2023). Avanzando hacia la resiliencia y sostenibilidad de las áreas de montaña en Europa. El proyecto MOVING. In *Revista de Fomento Rural*. <https://doi.org/10.32418/rfs.2023.307.5326>

- Esgalhado, C., Pinto-Correia, T., Targetti, S., Napoleone, C., & Rivera, M. (2024). Sustaining altitude pastures in mountain landscapes—a fuzzy cognitive model approach. *The Science of the Total Environment*, 172930. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.172930>
- Mainali, K., Arion, F. H., Rogozan, C. (2024). Analysis of Optional Quality Term (OQT) Mountain Label from producer’s perspective: study of mountainous counties surrounding Braşov, Romania. In Scientific Papers. Series “Management, Economic Engineering In Agriculture and Rural Development”. Print ISSN 2284-7995. E-ISSN 2285-3952. [volume 24 1 2024.pdf \(usamv.ro\)](https://www.usamv.ro/volume_24_1_2024.pdf)
- Mainali, K., Arion, F. H., Rogozan, C. (2024). Consumer understanding and perception of mountain label in the city of Braşov, Romania. In Scientific Papers. Series “Management, Economic Engineering in Agriculture and Rural Development”. Print ISSN 2284-7995. E-ISSN 2285-3952. [volume 24 1 2024.pdf \(usamv.ro\)](https://www.usamv.ro/volume_24_1_2024.pdf)
- Moretti, M., Belliggiano, A., Grando, S., Felici, F., Scotti, I., Ievoli, C., Blackstock, K., Delgado-Serrano, M. M., & Brunori, G. (2023). Characterizing value chains’ contribution to resilient and sustainable development in European mountain areas. *Journal of Rural Studies*, 100, 103022. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrurstud.2023.103022>
- Scotti, I., Ievoli, C., Bindi, L., Bispini, S., & Belliggiano, A. (2023). Facing climate vulnerability in mountain areas: The role of rural Actors’ agency and situated knowledge production. *Sustainability*, 15(22), 15877. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su152215877>
- Vavvos, A., Kafkalas, I., Piteris, C., & Skrapaliori, K. (2024). Climate change and the role of governance in the value chain sustainability of carob flour in Rethymno, Crete, Greece. In *Cooperative management* (pp. 139–147). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-49845-9_8

At the time this deliverable was completed, additional scientific articles are under the review process. These articles related to the latest deliverables produced and submitted by the MOVING partners.

4.3.5. Policy outreach

The emerging project results were shared with the EU institutions at a moment where the post 2027 policies for mountain areas are being developed in preparation for the new 2024-2029 EU Term and the tabling of the 2027-2034 Multi Annual Financial Framework by July 2024.

For this reason, a specific attention was given into presenting and disseminating the MOVING Policy Roadmap and Policy Recommendations during the third EU MAP meeting, the MOVING Scientific Conference and the MOVING Final Conference. Gathering policy experts and representatives from institutions or relevant stakeholder groups, these events offered a platform to comment and discuss the project’s contribution to policy.

Evidence from the MOVING policy outputs was included in the drafting of two key CoR opinions ["EU budget and place-based policies: proposals for new design and delivery mechanisms in the](#)

[MFF post-2027](#)" (Maupertuis, in preparation) and "[Enhancing Cohesion Policy support for regions with geographic and demographic handicaps \(art 174 TFEU\)](#)" (Maupertuis, CoR-2022-02959) as AEIDL experts acted as technical draftsman of both opinions.

Furthermore, AEIDL contributed in written form to the Committee of the Regions (CoR) Opinion [The Future of the Common Agricultural Policy](#) (Gomes-Galbecki , CoR-2023-05512), and both in written form as well as giving evidence in person by AEIDL experts to the Opinion [Targets and tools for a Smart Rural Europe](#) (Srsen, CoR-2022-04320), "How to exploit the full potential of cohesion policy to tackle demographic change" (García, COTER-VII/043) and the Opinion of the European Economic and Social Committee (EESC) "[Towards a greater involvement of Member States, Regions and Civil Society actors in the implementation of the Long-Term Vision for the EU's Rural Areas \(LTVRA\)](#)" (Decoster, NAT/914-EESC-2023).

On April 10, 2024, AREPO organised a [policy conference](#) at the EU Committee of the Regions on the new Regulation on Geographical Indications. The MOVING Contribution on the Optional Quality Term on mountain product was presented by AREPO, Highclere Consulting and Euromontana.

Crucially, both the Committee of the Regions, European Parliament, EU Economic and Social Committee and European Commission officials actively contributed to the finalisation of the MOVING Roadmap at the project's Final Conference, and as a follow up a detailed dissemination of the roadmap with key EU officials as well as new members elected after the June elections is planned for the 2nd part of 2024 as part of MOVING exploitation and dissemination activities after project ends.

5. DECO training and guidelines

A Communication Task Force was established in the first months of the project to ensure better coordination of the project's communication efforts and increase its outreach throughout both the project and partner organisations' channels and networks. It brings together one contact person per organisation within the consortium.

AEIDL produced a set of communication guidelines containing information on the Communication Task Force, language and writing style, use of social media, blog posts, press releases, EU acknowledgement and disclaimer usage, and the monitoring tool for communication and dissemination activities.

During the Years 3 and 4, WP1 leaders have facilitated two training sessions, as described in the following table:

Table 16. Overview of DECO trainings

Timing	Training and guidance	Content covered
March 2023	Drop-in session: M&E Tool for Regional MAPs	<p>The Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E) Tool is a shared spreadsheet designed to keep track of and reflect on the performance and engagement of the MOVING MAPs. In addition, the data supports the preparation of the D1.3 MOVING CoP design and implementation report, D1.4 Activity report year 1-2 [M24], as well as D6.3 Activity report year 3-4 [M48], and the Technical Reports of the project due in M36 and M48.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Analysis & main results of the M&E tool [M22] • Q&A from partners when filling and updating the tool in M34 (June 2023) • Learn from results achieved
June 2023	MOVING Exploitation workshop	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduction to the Exploitation: concepts, strategies, activities • MOVING Exploitation: what has been done so far • MOVING Exploitation: plan update • Barriers & enablers for MOVING Exploitation

Source: MOVING H2020

By means of the survey carried out in 2024, the Communication Task Force expressed their request for training and specific support in the project's final phase. It particularly emerged the need to foster partners' ability to produce briefs and synthetised content, engage with policy and decision-makers to disseminate the project's results, and writing news and press releases.

Figure 49. Areas for guidance and training

Source: MOVING H2020

6. MOVING Key Performance Indicators for impact

Since the start of the project in September 2020, the consortium has carried out numerous communication activities. The initial DECO Strategy (D1.1), submitted in M6, and the final DECO Strategy (D1.6), submitted in M40, outline a set of Key Performance Indicators (KPI) as defined in the Grant Agreement. Table 1 presents an overview of the status of KPIs achieved by the project with respect to initial targets, as specified in the DECO Strategy (D1.6).

Overall, significant progress has been made. In the case of the website metrics, the targets were exceeded due to increased promotion, the adoption of a multi-channel strategy and valuable content. For instance, this is the case for social media impressions, number of unique website visitors and visits to the Value Chain (VC) map and inventory.

Regarding social media indicators, most targets were exceeded, reflecting successful professional networking, community engagement, strong visual content appeal, and high visibility and reach. However, the target for Twitter followers was not fully achieved, even though figures achieved were very close to the final target and exceeded most of other projects' followership. In these terms, LinkedIn and Facebook showed to be a more engaging dissemination and communication tool to engage MOVING audiences.

In addition, the final number of newsletter subscribers was slightly lower than initially planned. As all content included in the newsletter was shared and promoted via social media networks, this has not been a major issue for the communication and dissemination of the project.

. Monitoring of Key Performance Indicators¹¹

Communication Output	KPI	Target (M48)	Achievement (M22)	Achievement (M48)
Website	Number of downloads of documents from the MOVING website	2 500	1 459	7 371
	Number of page views on MOVING website	50 000	28 871	83 695
	Number of unique visitors	15 000	4 512	17417
	Number of visits to the VC map & inventory	1 000	At the moment the number of views/visitors reflects those that viewed/downloaded/clicked on the deliverable 4.1 and the related infographic. The download figure will be provided at RP2.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Total: 4 438 • MOVING Infographic of the 23 selected VCs: 253 downloads • D4.1 Inventory of Mountain Value Chains: 99 downloads • D4.2 List of selected value chains: 42 downloads • MOVING Infographic value chains: 38 downloads • 340 clicks on the Story Maps website • 250 visits to the Story Maps website • 3 416 views to the Reference Region section
Social media	No of Twitter followers	1 000	604	966
	No of LinkedIn followers	800	259	995

¹¹ Data included in this table was extracted on 1, 2 and 5 August 2024 from different sources as Google Analytics, META/Facebook Business Suite and Twitter Analytics.

	No of Facebook followers	300	166	353
	No of Instagram followers	300	146	328
	No of Social Media impressions	400 000	220 611	463 733
	No of views in YouTube to the videos + webinars	3 500	1 318 views plus 111 extra views of videos currently unlisted or private because they were updated or modified	4 896 views plus 185 extra views of videos currently unlisted or private because they were updated or modified
Newsletter	Number of subscribers to the Newsletter	350	222	336
Synergies	No of meetings from H2020 project in which MOVING participated	12	4	18
MOVING App	No of download	200	App not yet developed	70 ¹²

Source: MOVING H2020

The table below provides a summary of MOVING outcomes and respective results in communication and dissemination, as planned in the Grant Agreement. Overall, the MOVING project has demonstrated strong engagement and dissemination efforts, leading to significant visibility and impact. While some targets were not fully met, the overall achievements highlight the project's success in reaching and engaging its intended audience.

In certain cases, web downloads of project's deliverables were not achieved. This discrepancy suggests that while some users may have viewed the document online without downloading it, others may have downloaded it. Furthermore, more concise and easy-to-grasp dissemination outputs (i.e. news items, blog posts, videos, infographics) were developed to complement the dissemination efforts. These products suited the best the interest of our target audiences by delivering key highlights of the given (sometimes lengthy) documents as informed by our assessment survey.

Some of the below mentioned deliverables were produced in the last months of the project and just before the summer break. Therefore, dissemination efforts have not been concluded yet. Justifications for those targets not been met is provided in the footnotes.

¹² Estimate as of end M48 according to UCO technical services, as some have been done from VRE, the two most important App stores and the web, where number of downloads is not available.

Table 17. MOVING outputs and communication/dissemination¹³

Respective Deliverable/output	Targeted in the Grant Agreement		Achievement (M48)
D2.1: Conceptual and analytical framework (June 2021, June 2023)	4 000	social media impressions & post reads	6 742
	300	web downloads	144 ¹⁴
	500	views	266 ¹⁵
	4	Papers	4
	1	peer review publication	2
	2	Workshop	2
	1	Practice Abstracts	1
	1	Policy brief	1
D3.2: Vulnerability map for each of the 23 reference regions	4 000	social media impressions & post reads	3882 ¹⁶
	300	web downloads	3381
	150	CoP members	283
	23	Visualisations	23
	1	peer review publication	1. Other articles submitted, pending for review and acceptance
	1	podcast	1
	1	Video	1
D4.1: Inventory of Mountain value chains	8 000	social media impressions & post reads	8 755

¹³ Data included in this table was extracted on 5 August 2024 from different sources as Google Analytics, META/Facebook Business Suite, Twitter Analytics, YouTube Studio, and the internal communication and dissemination tool. Additionally, data from Zenodo was also considered for views and downloads.

¹⁴ The availability of a video explaining the content of the document and other dissemination products (e.g. news, newsletters, social media promotion) may have served as an alternative to the document, reducing the necessity for downloads.

¹⁵ Promotion was made through a news item and an explanatory video, which may have led to the document receiving fewer views. The article and video might have provided enough information, making it unnecessary for people to consult the entire document.

¹⁶ The slightly lower number is attributed to the promotion being conducted during the final phase of the project and the content primarily appealing to researchers, which may have limited its broader reach.

	500	web downloads	155 ¹⁷
	1	peer review publication	0
	150	CoP members	278
D4.6: Global Upgrading Strategy	4 000	social media impressions & post reads	4 907
	300	web downloads	139 ¹⁸
	23	Digital Stories	23 ¹⁹
	2	peer review publication	0
	23	Practice Abstracts	31
D5.1: Comparative cross-case report on Mountain Value Chains	4 000	social media impressions & post reads	4 813
	300	web downloads	121 ²⁰
	4	peer review publication	0
	1	Policy brief	5
	1	Webinar	1
	1	podcast	1
D6.2: Foresight report including set of foresight maps	10 000	social media impressions & post reads	7 146 ²¹
	500	web downloads	Deliverable is confidential, so there's not downloads.
	1	Webinar ²²	1
	1	podcast	1
	150	CoP members	286

¹⁷ The lower number of downloads is likely due to the document's length and the availability of other promotional materials, such as Story Maps and an infographic summarising the content, as a result the latter were preferred by web visitors.

¹⁸ Dissemination occurred through several products, including a podcast episode and social media activity. These products were preferred by MOVING followers to web downloads of the entire document.

¹⁹ This target refers to vulnerability (T4.5) and was fully achieved.

²⁰ This deliverable was published in the last months of the project and its promotion and dissemination is still ongoing. Updated figures will be available in the coming months.

²¹ Dissemination occurred through several products, including news items and social media activity. This deliverable is confidential only and therefore this might have hindered from the achievement of this KPI.

²² Webinars for D6.2, D6.3 and D7.1 were merged into one.

D6.3: Synthesis report, including a Repertoire of Strategic Options	10 000	social media impressions & post reads	815 ²³
	500	web downloads	60 ²⁴
	1	Policy brief	1
	1	Video	1
	1	Webinar	1
	1	podcast	1
	150	CoP members	286
	2	peer review publication	N/A ²⁵ Articles submitted, pending for review and acceptance
D7.1: Policy Roadmap including recommendations for a new generation of public policies and strategies for Europe's mountain areas	10 000	social media impressions & post reads	D7.1 not available by the time this report was done
	300	web downloads	
	1	peer review publication	N/A ²⁶
	2 000	views on the policy roadmap	Policy Roadmap not available by the time this report was done
	1	Webinar	1
	1	podcast	1
	150	CoP members	286
	1	policy tool	Policy Tool not available by the time this report was done
1	Video	Video not available by the time this report was done. It is planned to be released by the end of the project	
Articles/conference papers	6 000	social media impressions & post reads	11 008
	500	Views	3 514 ²⁷

²³ Dissemination occurred during the final phase of the project through several products, including a blog article, video, and podcast episode. The deliverable is lengthy, and since the repertoire of strategic options are not available individually, this may have discouraged users from downloading the main document.

²⁴ This document was produced in the last phase of the project therefore promotion is still ongoing at the time being.

²⁵ As the deliverable was submitted during the final phase of the project, there was not enough time to publish the peer-reviewed articles.

²⁶ At the time this deliverable was developed, D7.1 was also under preparation, leaving no time to publish a peer-reviewed article.

²⁷ Data taken from news and events pages views, and the number of reports downloaded.

Practice Abstracts	6 000	social media impressions & post reads	5 598 ²⁸
	800	Views	889
	450	downloads	714
Web tool on value chain vulnerability	5 000	Web visitors	174 ²⁹
Web tool on policy design	3 000	Web visitors	Tool not available by the time this deliverable was developed
Videos & digital stories on Vulnerability of VC & mountain areas	3 000	Views	2 124 ³⁰
Videos & digital stories Strategic Options	3 000	Views	341 ³¹
Videos & digital stories Policy Roadmap & recommendations	3 000	Views	Video not available by the time this deliverable was developed
Videos & digital stories 23 storytelling video and/or infographics (reference regions)	6000	Views	8 723 ³²

Source: MOVING H2020

7. Exploitation Plan

7.1. Introduction to MOVING Exploitation

The exploitation plan constitutes the exploitation strategy during the project lifetime. Exploitation refers to the **process of making use of the MOVING’s results after the project end in order**

²⁸ The number is slightly lower than the target due to the missing set of practice abstracts by the time this deliverable was developed.

²⁹ The web tool was developed during the final phase of the project and is being subject to targeted promotion right up to the end of the project and beyond. That said, the niche nature of the content, which primarily appeals to a specialized scientific audience, likely contributed to the lower-than-expected engagement, though it is expected that present numbers will grow during 2024.

³⁰ Data taken from Digital stories and WP3 promotional video views of YouTube. Despite a targeted social media campaign aimed at key representatives, the failure to achieve the target may be attributed to factors such as the saturation of similar content, or potential mismatches between the content and audience interests.

³¹ The video was promoted in August 2024, when fewer people are active on social media, leading to fewer views. Dissemination will continue after the project’s end.

³² Data taken from Digital Stories website views, general Reference Regions website views, each Reference Regions website views, infographic, digital stories views.

to generate find and long-lasting benefits. In MOVING, exploitation revolves around getting stakeholders to effectively use the developed tools. MOVING results have a strong public nature. The methodologies and tools developed during MOVING will be made fully available to potential users through toolkits. AEIDL (WP1 Leader) and the Communications Task Force will coordinate the exploitation activities.

While dissemination of MOVING's knowledge and progress will be important to raise awareness of the project's tools and results, this alone will not guarantee the maximum possible long-term impact of the project's work. Therefore, concrete actions will be taken to ensure that end-users take advantage of and use the results and tools developed to achieve the project's objectives.

The key concepts of the exploitation plan are:

- **Result:** Any tangible or intangible output of the action, such as data, knowledge and information whatever their form or nature, whether or not they can be protected, which are generated in the action as well as any attached rights, including intellectual property rights.
- **Exploitation:** the use of results for commercial purposes, further research, education, or in public policymaking.
- **Exploitation route(s)/ potential use:** commercial/industrial, academic, societal and policy.
- **Key Exploitable Result (KER):** an identified main interesting result (as defined above) which has been selected and prioritised due to its high potential to be “exploited” – meaning to make use and derive benefits- downstream the value chain of a product, process or solution, or act as an important input to policy, further research or education.

7.2. Objectives of the exploitation plan

The main goal of the exploitation plan is to make use of the results of the project towards the end of the project and beyond. The **specific objectives** are to:

- Identify the main exploitable results, who is the owner and what the exploitation route will be;
- Analyse the commitments and responsibilities of the project partners in the exploitation activities to be carried out;
- Define the objectives and expected added value for the main stakeholders/target audience/end-user of the exploitable results;
- Present an overview of how the exploitable results will be used by key stakeholders;
- Ensure a sustainable impact of the project after the end of the funding period.

7.3. Methodology

In MOVING, the exploitation plan has been designed and developed through an **iterative co-creation process** which involved all project partners, including regional MAPs, begun already in the first half of the project. The Exploitation activities are led by AEIDL (WP1 Leader) in strong

concertation with the project’s coordinator (UCO). Figure 50 illustrates the key steps undertaken to define the MOVING’s exploitation strategy all along the project’s implementation.

Figure 50. The development process for the MOVING’s exploitation along the project’s implementation

Source: MOVING H2020

At the early stage of the project’s implementation (M6), an initial plan of MOVING Exploitation Strategy was outlined in D1.6 DECO Strategy. This plan guided the first activities towards the identification of MOVING KERs, exploitation objectives, and exploitation actions (either joint or individuals). By M18, MOVING exploitation plan was proposed and developed through partners’ contribution and first co-creation workshop on exploitation.

By M34, this plan was further detailed based on the project’s developments through a co-creation workshop taking place on **22 June 2023 (online)**, under the lead of AEIDL, and led to the partners’ revision of the MOVING KERs and exploitation activities. This revision was used as solid foundations to further refine the project’s exploitation roadmap by AEIDL, the coordinator and the Horizon Booster Service. The output is the MOVING Exploitation Roadmap, which has been integrated into the D1.6 DECO Strategy and shared to partners.

Finally, a conclusive **workshop** was organised by UCO in June 2024 back-to-back to the project’s General Assembly. During this workshop, partners reflected on the legacy of the project in relation to the MOVING Exploitation Strategy and discussed upon lead actions for making it happen. Results from all described steps occurred in years 3 and 4 are presented below. It follows an outline of the project’s Exploitation Roadmap, which is provided in Annex III MOVING Exploitation.

7.4. Outputs from Exploitation co-creation activities

Co-creation workshop (M34)

An Exploitation co-creation workshop was held in June 2023 and involved the MOVING partners and WP Leaders. AEIDL facilitated a discussion revolved around four main points: i) Introduction to exploitation (concepts, strategies and activities); ii) MOVING Exploitation: task and work done up to date; iii) MOVING Exploitation: Plan update; iv) Next steps.

During this working meeting, partners looked back at the MOVING Exploitation plan realised in the Years 3 and 4 of the project, as defined under the Exploitation Strategy of the [D1.6 DECO Activity Strategy \(initial\)](#). The workshop discussion aimed at revising and prioritising the project's exploitation actions along the four axes set up in the Exploitation Strategy (Figure 51):

- **Methodological guidelines and capacities**, denoting the project's contribution on providing a replicable and scalable conceptual framework on Mountain Value Chains' upgrading and providing methodological guidelines on the process for implementing such concepts;
- **Evidence and Results from Value Chains**, incorporating the outputs, data, reports and gathered knowledge from the 23 MOVING Reference Regions across WPs;
- **Community of Practice**, as the science-society-policy interface consolidating the project's results through a network of engaged and mobilised stakeholders operating at both local/regional and EU levels;
- **Policy Toolkit**, gathering resources for policy work and recommendations emerged from the project's evidence.

Figure 51. MOVING's Exploitation Plan. MOVING Co-creation workshop (M34).

Source: MOVING H2020

Figure 52. Guidelines for the MOVING Exploitation Plan Updated and four areas of exploitation's work. MOVING Co-creation workshop (M34).

3. MOVING Exploitation: plan update

MOVING_Key Exploitable Results

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100%

Identify, within the Work Package you lead (or other Work Packages), the Key Exploitable Results that MOVING is developing. If the KEER has already been included because it was mentioned in the Start Agreement, please fill in the next sheet.

Filling-in instructions	
Sheets Please, read carefully these instructions before filling the spreadsheet. Find in light yellow the part that need to be completed	
Key Concepts	Exploitation the use of results for commercial purposes, further research, education, or in public policymaking. Result Any tangible or intangible output of the action, such as data, knowledge and information whatever their form or nature, whether or not they can be protected, which are generated by the action as well as any affected rights, including intellectual property rights. Key Exploitable Result (KER) An identified main interesting result (as defined above) which has been selected and prioritized due to its high potential to be exploited – meaning to make use and derive benefits, demonstrate the value chain of a product, process or solution, or set an important step to policy, further research or education. Exploitation route means a sequence to exploit a specific KER. Some examples could be: to write a scientific publication, to prepare a training kit to deliver a training within your own organisation, to develop a market product etc.
	Steps towards completion (optional) WP LEADERS 1. Fill in columns A, C and the KEERs appropriate following instructions in rows 10, 11 of this sheet. VCO, AEDL, WP LEADERS, and VCO & AEDL 2. Final list of KEERs and draft Exploitation Plan will be included in D1.4.1024 and the Periodic Report to be submitted after WP4.
	Key Exploitable results WP LEADERS Identify, within the Work Package you lead (or other Work Packages), the Key Exploitable Results that MOVING is developing. If the KEER has already been included because it was mentioned in the Start Agreement, please fill in the rest of the columns and update relevant information if needed. WP LEADERS For each KEER identified, please add the name of partners that own the result. It could appear the partner that will lead the exploitation activities.
	B. Outcome(s) of result WP LEADERS For each KEER, please indicate if possible with a short description of the result. D. E. F. G. Exploitation route WP LEADERS Please indicate which exploitation route is the most appropriate for the result. If possible, a specific activity or exploitation pathway should be added. H. Potential users WP LEADERS For each KEER, identify the results should identify potential users. If possible, be specific and for each user add the name and the country (e.g. CH24, Italy). The filling with suggestions from the KEERs.
Joint exploitation	Key Concepts WP LEADERS joint exploitation the use of results that entails the participation of one or more MOVING partners.
	Steps towards completion (optional) WP LEADERS 1. Fill in columns A, C, D, E, F, G, H. All partners As reported in the "KER" sheet. Please add any other KEERs that you think might be interesting and you might want to exploit. This can be something else than the deliverable (e.g. a dataset, the WPB network, CoPs). All partners As reported in the "KER" sheet. All partners For each KEER, please indicate your name if you would like to exploit the respective KEER. All partners For each KEER, please indicate your name if you would like to exploit the respective KEER. D. E. F. Exploitation routes, target audiences, KEERs All partners For each KEER, please identify the exploitation routes that you would be using, the target audiences and 50% for monitoring and evaluation. This exploitation routes will be further documented in a follow-up stage in dialog with other MOVING partners that expressed their interest to exploit the joint product. All partners For each KEER, please indicate your name if you would like to exploit the respective KEER. Please fill in any barrier or enabler that should be considered.
	A. Key exploitable results All partners As reported in the "KER" sheet. B. Outcome(s) of result All partners As reported in the "KER" sheet. C. Partners involved All partners For each KEER, please indicate your name if you would like to exploit the respective KEER. D. E. F. Exploitation routes, target audiences, KEERs All partners For each KEER, please identify the exploitation routes that you would be using, the target audiences and 50% for monitoring and evaluation. This exploitation routes will be further documented in a follow-up stage in dialog with other MOVING partners that expressed their interest to exploit the joint product. All partners For each KEER, please indicate your name if you would like to exploit the respective KEER. Please fill in any barrier or enabler that should be considered.
	H. Potential users All partners For each KEER, identify the results should identify potential users. If possible, be specific and for each user add the name and the country (e.g. CH24, Italy). The filling with suggestions from the KEERs.
Individual exploitation	Key Concepts WP LEADERS individual exploitation the use of results that entails the participation of one single MOVING partner.
	Steps towards completion (optional) WP LEADERS 1. Fill in columns A, C, D, E, F, G, H. All partners As reported in the "KER" sheet. Please add any other KEERs that you think might be interesting and you might want to exploit. This can be something else than the deliverable (e.g. a dataset, the WPB network, CoPs). All partners As reported in the "KER" sheet. All partners For each KEER, please indicate your name if you would like to exploit the respective KEER. All partners For each KEER, please indicate your name if you would like to exploit the respective KEER. D. E. F. Exploitation routes, target audiences, KEERs All partners For each KEER, please identify the exploitation routes that you would be using, the target audiences and 50% for monitoring and evaluation. This exploitation routes will be further documented in a follow-up stage in dialog with other MOVING partners that expressed their interest to exploit the joint product. All partners For each KEER, please indicate your name if you would like to exploit the respective KEER. Please fill in any barrier or enabler that should be considered.
	A. Key exploitable results All partners As reported in the "KER" sheet. B. Outcome(s) of result All partners As reported in the "KER" sheet. C. Partners involved All partners For each KEER, please indicate your name if you would like to exploit the respective KEER. D. E. F. Exploitation routes, target audiences, KEERs All partners For each KEER, please identify the exploitation routes that you would be using, the target audiences and 50% for monitoring and evaluation. This exploitation routes will be further documented in a follow-up stage in dialog with other MOVING partners that expressed their interest to exploit the joint product. All partners For each KEER, please indicate your name if you would like to exploit the respective KEER. Please fill in any barrier or enabler that should be considered.
	H. Potential users All partners For each KEER, identify the results should identify potential users. If possible, be specific and for each user add the name and the country (e.g. CH24, Italy). The filling with suggestions from the KEERs.

Elements to be updated are in yellow/orange

MOVING_Key Exploitable Results.xlsx - Google Sheets

2. MOVING Exploitation: areas of work

Source: MOVING H2020

Exploitation plan update (M36)

In the aftermath of the co-creation workshop (M34), WP Leaders and project’s partners were asked to provide an update reading of the MOVING’s Key Exploitable Results (KERs), as well as of joint and individual exploitation plans. As part of this revision, **19 Key Exploitable Results** were identified by project partners. For each result, the owner of the results, a description, and exploitation routes (commercial/industrial, academic, societal, policy) were updated, and potential users were identified.

Overall, **5 potential joint exploitation activities** were identified, detailed, and clustered as part of four macro-categories (MOVING Value Chains, MOVING methodological guidelines and capacities, MOVING Policy Toolkit, MOVING Community of Practice). At individual partner level, **24 potential individual exploitation activities** were expressed by the MOVING partners. Figure 54 provides an overview of individual exploitation actions identified by MOVING partners by M36, and Figure 53 illustrates the type of exploitation route (i.e. political, academic, societal, all). Barriers and enablers have been described for both the potential joint and individual partners’ strategies for exploitation.

	Total = 24
<i>Advocacy</i>	6
<i>Educational/Recreational activity</i>	3
<i>Pilot/project</i>	3
<i>Tools</i>	2
<i>Report</i>	2
<i>Master thesis</i>	2
<i>Academic teaching</i>	2
<i>Exploit the Network</i>	1
<i>Research project</i>	1
<i>Training courses</i>	1
<i>Capacity building (package)</i>	1

Figure 54 Individual exploitation activities (number) in MOVING

Figure 53 Individual Exploitation routes identified in MOVING (by type)

Source: MOVING H2020

Exploitation Roadmap (M43)

During the final project’s phase (from September 2023 onwards), the **Horizon Booster services** were consulted to deliver the final version of the MOVING Exploitation plan based on information

and feedback gathered in the previous steps of the process. The Horizon Booster is the European Commission's appointed service designed to accompany Horizon projects in drafting, detailing and delivering a ready-to-go exploitation strategy.

Under the lead of AEIDL and UCO, in consultation with project's partners, the MOVING project further refined its exploitation strategy in alignment with the Horizon Booster recommendations and templates. As part of this process, the MOVING KERs were further defined, and primary project's results were prioritised under each of the KER. In conclusion, **three main KERs were opted by MOVING as central component of the project's exploitation plan:**

- The MOVING Conceptual Analytical Framework;
- The MOVING Regional Tools: 23 Mountain Areas Vulnerabilities and Opportunities through Value Chains;
- The MOVING Policy Tools.

For each of the above-mentioned KERs, the MOVING Exploitation strategy details:

- **A characterisation for each KER**, encompassing a KER's description, unique selling point, alternative solutions, target market, go to market strategies;
- **Use options**, describing priority activities to exploit the KER, detailing between direct and indirect uses;
- **An exploitation roadmap**, outlining key steps to enable the effective use of the KER, revenue streams, financial costs, impact in the medium-term;
- **A risk-assessment and priority map**, identifying and evaluating the probability and impacts of risk factors which might hinder the project's exploitation.

The Table below summarises key elements of the **MOVING's exploitation roadmap**. For each of the three identified KERs, background elements, use options, target market, impact (3-years' time) and major risks. The detailed version of the project's exploitation strategy, as developed with the Horizon Booster services, is available in Annex III.

Additionally, the **short-term actions** pointed out in the conclusive General Assembly are indicated in the column on the right. These actions represent the initial steps towards the rolling out of the exploitation roadmap set up by the project. For matters of simplifications and confidentiality, actions have been clustered as most relevant.

Table 18. MOVING Exploitation (Short version)

KERs	Background	Use Options	Target market	Impact in a 3-year time	Major Risk Factors	Short-term actions emerged at the General Assembly
Conceptual Analytical Framework	D2.4 Conceptual analytical framework (final version)	Direct use: a new research project pursued	Scientific audience (e.g., Universities, research centres)	Deepen the understanding of mountain value chains' interactions and dynamics; Contribute to identify key points for leveraging mountain value chains' enhancement	Weak exploitation: Inadequate business plan; CAF having gaps and inconsistencies; Disagreement on further investments: some partners may leave, Disagreement on ownership rules. Remedial action: Definition of a clear exploitation strategy; through peer review of CAF; complying with Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement's contractual arrangements and duties; Deploying existing technical infrastructure and expertise.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Apply the MOVING CAF to investigate on a larger perimeter - Adopt the Value Chains' building concept and approach in the H2020 MERLIN project - Expand the CAP by including the Social Reproduction and Alternative Economic Initiatives
23 Mountain Areas Vulnerabilities and Opportunities through Value Chains	D3.1 Land Use Systems and Land Cover Map in 23 Reference Regions D3.2 Land use systems and vulnerability matrixes and vulnerability maps for the 23 reference regions	Indirect use: spin-off services	Mountain value chains' actors, in particular businesses and practitioners (from different sectors: tourism, agriculture, forestry); Regional Decision Makers Regional and local authorities; Wannabe-entrepreneurs	Increase the capacity of mountain value chains' actors to address current and future threats; Identify, improve and rollout upgrading strategies for mountain value chains; Develop a network of regional mountain stakeholders improved skills	Limited uptake by Mountain Value Chains; Partners break out and create competitive products; Lack of technological structure to collect all tools together. Remedial action: active promotion of tool directly with MVCs; complying with Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement's contractual arrangements and duties;	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Develop mountain valorisation initiatives with local/regional institutions building up on the CoP community - Engage the CoP in future research, project and communication activities - Organise cross-case visits - Use knowledge gathered to apply for new funding streams - Develop a project on product certification - Use results to train other Value Chains in the same country area - Connect pioneer farmers through citizen science approach to foster innovation - Train industrial actors on MOVING results

						<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Apply the MOVING's results to work on Knowledge Economy projects - Use the results to enrich the rural Hungarian territorial quality system - Use and further develop the project's results in the Horizon GI SMART and VISIONARY projects - Prepare scientific publications - Develop a result-based scheme for mountain pastures in the Portuguese mountain region
Policy Tools	<p>D2.5 Final set of Policy briefs</p> <p>D7.1 Policy Roadmap including the results of the Policy Audit and recommendations for a new generation of public policies and strategies for Europe's Mountain areas</p> <p>D7.2 Policy Design Toolkit</p> <p>D6.3 Synthesis report, including a Repertoire of Strategic Options</p>	Indirect use: development of a new legislation/standard	Policy and decision-makers at local, regional, national and European levels	Ensure that MOVING's results are reflected in a number of key European, national and regional policies and strategies; Raise capacity-building initiatives, programmes and projects to enhance mountain resilience and sustainability	<p>Market Demand. Products are not developed in proper timing, Limited uptake from EU decision makers; No resources (human and/or financial) secured to make the next step toward exploitation.</p> <p>Remedial action: policy tools made in sync with evolving EU policy cycle and actively promoted at key decision making stages; Reliance over advocacy groups within MOVING network and other EU stakeholder networks.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Present MOVING's results to policy makers in order to improve policy on regional Mountain Value Chains - Use and further develop the project's recommendations in the Horizon GI SMART project - Use MOVING's policy findings and results to contribute to post-2027 policy consultations and discussions - Consolidate and take forward the policy recommendations with Euromontana and other regional/national interest groups (e.g. Romanian National Agency of Mountain Areas)

Towards the operationalisation of MOVING Exploitation Plan (M46)

In June 2024, a conclusive workshop on the project's legacy was organised with all project's partners as part of the MOVING Final General Assembly. The MOVING partners identified **50 actions for the ensuring a continuation of the project's legacy and an uptake of its results** after the project's end. (Figure 55). These actions are a step forward the operationalisation of the MOVING Exploitation plan, as defined in the following subchapter.

Figure 55. Short-term actions for the operationalization of MOVING Exploitation plan, as part of the MOVING Final General Assembly (June 2024)

8. Lessons learned

Based on the analysis conducted, it can be concluded MOVING's communication and dissemination efforts are on the right track towards achieving its objectives and expected impact.

When it comes to communication channels, certain media platforms have proven more effective for project dissemination and communication, notably Twitter and LinkedIn. Recently, Facebook and Instagram have also shown an increasing presence, particularly for communicating and disseminating information about project in-person meetings and events.

Moreover, the project has faced overarching challenges, such as language barriers due to the lack of English proficiency among local participants. The support of partners in this task was crucial, particularly with the key outputs of the project. Engaging the media and getting project outputs covered in specialist EU media has also been challenging. For domestic media, collaboration with relevant national-local project partners has been necessary but still difficult.

Efforts have been made to tackle these challenges, but ongoing improvements and strategies are necessary to overcome them effectively. By recognising and addressing these obstacles, European projects can enhance their communication and dissemination efforts, ensuring the successful delivery of their outcomes and results.

In addition to this, MOVING has addressed in RP2 a number of strategic recommendations from reviewers as spelled out below:

- Reviewers requested enhanced communication and dissemination of the MOVING Policy outcomes towards RP3, which was addressed as follows:
 - Over the last project's phase, MOVING Policy outputs and proposals were discussed with project partners and stakeholders as well as external actors (including institutions and policy makers) in a number of events. Among these, MOVING Stakeholder Event in Budapest (Nov 2023), MOVING Scientific Conference (Apr 2024), AREPO General Assembly at the Committee of the Regions (Apr 2024), EU MAP Meeting (May 2024), MOVING Final Conference (June 2024).
 - The project contributed to a number of institutional consultations and opinions as described in the section on 'Policy outreach' above.
 - The final episode of the MOVING podcast particularly focusses on the project's policy contribution towards post-2027 EU policies.
 - Targeted dissemination of the MOVING Policy Roadmap and recommendations will be done by the end of the project and in the following period by AEIDL, UCO and other partners.
- Reviewers suggested to simplify the information and results provided by the project.
 - Audiovisual materials and infographics were prepared to deliver the final project's outputs.
 - The MOVING podcast provides a summary of the project's highlights emerged from its entire journey. The podcast consists of 5 episodes, lasting between 10 and 15 minutes.

- An update version of the project's website was released. This version provides a ['Results' Tab](#) gathering the main results of the project.
- An infographic on the [project's final results was](#) produced and delivered during the MOVING Final Conference as well as disseminated via the project's channels.
- Some MAPs produced specific content on the regional outputs of the project targeted to regional stakeholders and disseminated it in local language.
- Executive summaries have been included in the project's deliverables.
- Reviewers demanded to display in a more consistent and accessible form the MOVING Practice Abstracts.
 - Practice Abstracts are accessible via the [website](#). These documents are grouped by mountain region as they provide practical recommendations and lessons learnt for the given regions.
 - Visualisation of the Practice Abstract and cover page was included to make them more attractive for readers.

Further details and more comprehensive explanation of corrective actions will be provided in the final technical report.

Annex I. Key survey results

The purpose of the survey was to contribute to this self-assessment exercise by complementing the quantitative information collected in the analysis of key results progress towards achieving objectives. This survey consisted of 3 sections:

- Section 1: Communication
- Section 2: Dissemination and impact
- Section 3: Final recommendations

The survey was targeted to the projects' partners, and its results have been used to assess the effectiveness of the project's communication and dissemination strategies. The survey aimed to prioritise the target audience, understand how partners are using the communication channels and products of the project, recognise challenges faced in communicating about the project, and gather insights for improving communication efforts during the final phase of MOVING.

A total of 22 responses from 20 partners have been received during January 2024.

This annex includes the analysis of the main results of the survey. Some of the results obtained have been integrated throughout the deliverable in the corresponding section.

Section 1: Communication

Regarding communication, MOVING employs various channels to convey key messages and outcomes to stakeholders and target groups. Partners were asked to rate the usefulness of MOVING communication channels directly for them as project partners on a scale of 1 to 4, being 1 not useful and 4 very useful (see figure 56). The most highly rated channels were the Virtual Research Environment (3.64 score), followed by MOVING Newsletter (3.05 score), MOVING social media channels (2.82 score), and MOVING podcast (2.36 score) (N=22).

Figure 56. Usefulness of the MOVING communication channels for partners

Source: MOVING H2020

Also, partners were consulted about the usefulness of MOVING content based on their experience and knowledge. Publications, including research findings and deliverables, emerged as the most highly valued with 68,2% (15 respondents), followed by webinars and events with 63,6% (14 respondents), and videos, including partner interviews and events' sessions with 50% (11 respondents). Project news and blog posts, alongside visual elements such as leaflets, infographics and posters attracted 45,5% (10 respondents), while scientific articles and the MOVING newsletter garnered interest from 40,9% (9 respondents). MOVING podcast episodes were noted by 27,3% (6 respondents). Story Maps were deemed useful by 22,7% (5 respondents).

Figure 57. Usefulness of MOVING content for partners

Source: MOVING H2020

Regarding the MOVING website, partners were asked about the frequency of their visits. The survey revealed that 55% responded "Weekly", while 32% indicated visiting it "Monthly", and 9% visit it "Daily". Additionally, feedback from partners indicates high satisfaction with the website's usability and navigation, with 82% rating it as "Excellent" or "Very good" (N=22).

Figure 58. Frequency of visits on the MOVING website

Source: MOVING H2020

Figure 59. Usability and navigation of the MOVING website

Source: MOVING H2020

Partners were also asked how likely they are to recommend the MOVING website to colleagues or other stakeholders in their network. The survey revealed that 36% (8 respondents) answered “Very likely,” while 32% (7 respondents) mentioned “Somewhat likely.”

Section 2: Dissemination and impact

Partners were asked regarding how frequently they share MOVING results and updates with other actors. The 50% responded “Often”, while 45% answered “Sometimes”.

Furthermore, partners were asked about the main communication channels used to inform other actors about MOVING’s results. In this respect, through multi-choice responses, the 63,64% (14

respondents) of partners selected “Workshops and events organised by my organisation” as their primary channel. This was followed by 54,55% (12 respondents) who chose "Social Media accounts of my organisation" and "Email". The “Website of my organisation” was selected by the 36,36% (8 respondents) of the partners, while the “Personal social media accounts” was selected by the 31,82% (7 respondents). Only 22,73% (5 respondents) of respondents chose the "Newsletter of my organisation". Lastly, 27,27% (6 respondents) selected "Other" and provided examples such as press releases, phone calls, and newsletter to MAP members.

Figure 60. Main communication channels used to inform other actors about MOVING’s results

Source: MOVING H2020

Based on their experience and knowledge, partners were asked to assess the most effective channels to disseminate MOVING’s results with key audiences, rating them on a scale from 1 to 4, with 1 indicating "not useful" and 4 indicating "very useful". The ratings for each type of channel were as follows (N=22):

- Events and conferences (non-scientific): 3.55
- Targeted emails: 3.36
- Scientific journals: 3.09
- Media outlets, TV, radio, magazines: 3.09
- MOVING website: 3.09
- Scientific conferences: 3.00
- MOVING Newsletter: 2.91
- MOVING Podcast: 2.59

Figure 61. Most effective channels to disseminate MOVING’s results with key audiences

Source: MOVING H2020

Partners were asked to indicate what MOVING results would be the most relevant for future uptake and activities after the project’s end. Figure 62 displays the percentage of respondents (N=22) who chose each of the following MOVING results:

- The Conceptual and Analytical Framework: 19% of respondents.
- Findings and Tools for Mountain Regions: 31% of respondents.
- Policy Results (Recommendations, Audit, Toolkit): 45% of respondents.
- Others, such as StoryMaps, or personal connections with scientific and mountain stakeholder actors: 5% of respondents.

Figure 62. Most relevant MOVING result for future uptake

Source: MOVING H2020

Section 3: Final Recommendations

Partners were consulted how would qualify the communication and dissemination activities conducted by the project so far. It was asked to rate a series of statements linked to communication and dissemination activities from 2 to 5, being 2 disagree and 4 fully agree, and giving the option of *I don't know/have an opinion* (1). All statements were rated between 4.18 and 3.16 scores. The scores for each of them in order of most highly rated are:

- Communication materials and messages are clear and understandable (4.18 scores)
- Communication efforts align with and support the project's objectives (4.14 scores)
- Communication materials and messages are adequately tailored to key audiences (3.86 scores)
- Synergies are created with relevant initiatives or projects related to mountain ecosystems and value chains (3.64 scores)
- Results are appropriately disseminated to key audiences at local and regional level (3.59 scores)
- Results are appropriately disseminated to key audiences at local and regional level (3.45 scores).
- Results are appropriately disseminated to key audiences at national level (2.86 scores)

Additionally, partners outlined up to three areas in which they would have needed further guidance and training to improve MOVING dissemination until the project's end. The survey revealed that 33% (15 respondents) of partners chose "Producing briefs and synthesised content," while 24%

(11 respondents) chose "Engaging with policy and decision makers." "Writing news and press releases" was the third most chosen option, with 17% (8 respondents).

Figure 63. Areas for guidance and training

Source: MOVING H2020

Annex II. Categories to classify MOVING social media post

MOVING

- MOVING progress and results: this category refers to all posts including general updates and news about the project (e.g. consortium meetings, new sections of the website available, deliverables published)
- MOVING COP and MAPs: this category refers to all posts regarding activities of the MOVING Multi-Actor Platforms, both at regional and the EU MAP, as well as the Community in Practice.

External to MOVING:

- Other EU projects: this category refers to all posts that reference another Horizon 2020 project, or projects funded under different programmes, that are working on similar topics
- Other stakeholders: this category refers to all posts including information about the European institutions and linked networks (e.g. EC, CoR), other key EU players (e.g. ENRD, Euromontana, RUMRA), and international organisations (e.g. OECD, FAO, UN).

Annex III MOVING Exploitation

Characterisation Table

The Characterisation table is designed to start the collection of information that will be then reviewed and further integrated during the project life. Partners in charge of the Key Exploitable Result (KER) should fill in the content and discuss it with the ones involved in the finalisation of the KER including the partners that will oversee the testing phase.

KER: Conceptual Analytical Framework	
Problem	Lack of an overall analytical framework to analyse and evaluate mountain value chains' interactions with endogenous and exogenous elements, including with the socio-ecological systems.
Alternative solution	Other Conceptual Frameworks exist, though they do not specifically address mountain value chains. A few examples are listed below: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Filière (1960s), the flow of physical inputs and services in the production of a final product (filière of production, i.e., from input to output, or filière of product i.e. from output to input) (Lauret, 1983; Malassis, 1973); ● Commodity Chain (1970s), similar, derived by dependence theories (Wallerstein, 1974); ● Supply Chain (1980s), similar, more in a logistic management sense (Hugos, 2003); ● Global Commodity Chain (1990s), describing the shift in the organization of global production toward external networks (the so-called “outsourcing wave”) (Gereffi & Korzeniewicz, 1994); ● Global Value Chains (GVC 2000s), similar to the previous replacing commodity (that basically means raw undifferentiated material) with value intended as “value added” (Sturgeon, 2008); ● Netchains (2001), Integrating supply chain and network analyses (Lazzarini et al., 2001). ● Socio-Ecological Systems (McGinnis and Ostrom (2014).
Unique Selling Point USP - Unique Value Proposition UVP	MOVING Conceptual Analytical Framework provides a comprehensive approach to understanding, showcasing, and evaluating existing connections, forces and interactions with an impact on/originated from mountain value chains. It is the only conceptual framework focused on mountain value chains and their interactions with underpinning socio-ecological systems.
Description	The MOVING Conceptual Analytical Framework helps to disentangle and explain, with narrative and plain language, key factors, elements and dynamics of mountain value chains.
"Market" – Target market	This KER is intended for scientific audiences (i.e. research institutes, universities).

"Market" – Early Adopters	Scientific partners within the MOVING project.
"Market" - Competitors	Other researchers working on rural and mountain development issues, including EU projects (e.g. Horizon Europe MountResilience, COST Action MARGISTAR). Existing thematic organisations and networks (e.g. Euromontana, NEMOR, ICIMOD)
Go to Market – Use model	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open access scientific publication to make this KER accessible to a wider audience. • Use of this KER into scientific publications • Use of this KER for facilitating educational curricula
Go to Market - Timing	End of 2024/2025, once the final version of this KER will be available.
Go to Market – IPR Background	D2.4 Conceptual analytical framework (final version) [UNIFI]. No specific restrictions are foreseen for using this background.
Go to Market – IPR Foreground	Refinement of the Conceptual Framework, including application to case studies, further improvement etc. No restrictions are set.

Source: MOVING H2020

KER: 23 Mountain Areas Vulnerabilities and Opportunities through Value Chains	
Problem	Mountain value chains' actors lack practical tools to foster mountain resilience and their capacity to adapt to climate change and other threats.
Alternative solution	<p>Solutions and studies to enhance resilience somehow exist at the local and regional scales, concerning some relevant sectors for mountains (e.g. tourism, agriculture). However, such solutions are not available in all regions, they are often fragmented, and might not cover multiple sectors.</p> <p>At the European level, alternative solutions are the Adapt@Altitude platform, Euromontana's collection of successful practices, Interreg tools (e.g. Alpine Space, POCTEFA, Europe).</p> <p>At the global level, alternative solutions are the Mountain Partnership's best practices, MRI Research and Tools (incl. GeoMountains project).</p>
Unique Selling Point USP - Unique Value	MOVING developed different practical tools (e.g. maps, matrixes, guidelines, inspiring stories, good practices lists, practice abstracts) to build the capacities of local actors. The MOVING approach has been tested and validated across 23 mountain regions in Europe and it considers a variety of factors (social, environmental and economic). This provides our solution not only an integrated approach, but also

Proposition UVP	the widest set of practical tools – thus far – with the highest geographical coverage of Europe’s mountains.
Description	MOVING provides a number of tools for value chains’ actors across Europe’s mountain regions. Tools are intended to simplify and guide the improvement, upgrading and decision-making of mountain value chains to face with existing threats (e.g. climate change, demography).
"Market" – Target market	Mountain value chains’ actors, in particular businesses and practitioners (from different sectors: tourism, agriculture, forestry) Regional Decision Makers Regional and local authorities Wannabe-entrepreneurs
"Market" – Early Adopters	Mountain value chains’ actors in the MOVING Reference Regions, in particular: MOVING MAPs in 23 regions, CNVP members, AREPO members.
"Market" - Competitors	Different local and regional solutions might exist in different mountain areas. A few instances are local and regional research labs (e.g. Labex ITTEM, CEMONT), consultancies (e.g. ETIFOR), Local Action Groups in selected regions, regional authorities.
Go to Market – Use model	Training Capacity-building sessions Knowledge transfer events Sharing information on platforms
Go to Market - Timing	2024
Go to Market – IPR Background	The main components of this KER are ‘D3.1 Land Use Systems and Land Cover Map in 23 Reference Regions’ [UEvora] and ‘D3.2 Land use systems and vulnerability matrixes and vulnerability maps for the 23 reference regions’ [UCO]. Additional components: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● D4.3 Participatory analysis of value chains [CZU] ● D4.5 Report on Vulnerability and Resilience Performance of 23 Reference Region Value Chains [HUTTON] ● D3.3 Tools for science-society-policy interfaces (Story Maps) [CNR] ● D1.8 Practice Abstracts (1st batch) [UCO] ● D1.9 Practice Abstracts (2nd batch) [UCO] ● D4.1 Inventory of Mountain value chains [UNIFI] ● D4.7 31 Practice Abstracts [CZU]

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • D5.1 Comparative cross-case report on Mountain value chains [UCO] • D4.4 Digital stories from each reference region [CZU] <p>All components are accessible here: https://www.moving-h2020.eu/. No specific restrictions are foreseen for using this background, except for D3.3, for which the use of the D4Science Infrastructure is permitted in compliance with the following conditions (as set in the Consortium Agreement): “The use of all D4Science Infrastructure services is permitted, without prejudice to the provisions of the Policies and Terms of Use set forth in the following references: - https://www.iubenda.com/privacypolicy/441050; - https://services.d4science.org/cookiepolicy ; https://services.d4science.org/terms-of-use.</p>
Go to Market – IPR Foreground	Further refinement of the tools and adaptation of regional scale.

Source: MOVING H2020

KER: Policy Tools	
Problem	More adapted policy frameworks are needed to address the needs of actors along mountain value chains. Policymakers need support to design measures that target the unique needs of these actors.
Alternative solution	Existing policy framework and tools to support mountain value chains and mountain territorial development include national/regional tools (e.g. Avenir Montagne- France, SNAI-Italy, Catalan mountain law, Romanian mountain law), and EU policy frameworks (CAP, Cohesion Policy, Art 174/5 TFEU) and EU-level policy recommendations from relevant networks/organisations (e.g. Euromontana, EU Mountain Convention, Rural Networks, EU CAP Network on Mountains).
Unique Selling Point USP - Unique Value Proposition UVP	MOVING provides a set of policy tools that can be used to improve European, national and regional policy frameworks to support mountain value chains. These are actionable, focused and based on real stakeholder needs. MOVING Policy Tools have been co-developed and validated by more than 900 actors in 23 EU mountain regions. They have been derived in close connection with existing networks (e.g. Euromontana and AREPO) and they provide the ground for an enabling policy framework to address common challenges and shared solutions.
Description	MOVING provides an integrated set of policy tools to guide policy at local, regional, national and European levels. Making use of MOVING findings, is a quick way to improve the wellbeing and resilience of mountain regions in Europe.

"Market" – Target market	Policy and decision-makers at local, regional, national and European levels (e.g. EU Commission (DG Agri); European Parliament; European Committee of the Regions and European Economic and Social Committee; EU agri-food stakeholders participating in Civil Dialogue Groups; Regional authorities).
"Market" – Early Adopters	European and national-level policymakers.
"Market" - Competitors	Existing advocacy and lobbying networks who might have a different position than the one represented by MOVING (e.g. conventional and large farming organisations, COPA COGECA).
Go to Market – Use model	Policy tools will feed into ongoing policy discussion at multiple governing levels, providing evidence from mountain actors and ranges.
Go to Market - Timing	Mid-End of 2024
Go to Market – IPR Background	<p>Core components:</p> <p>D2.5 Final set of Policy briefs [UNIFI]</p> <p>D7.1 Policy Roadmap including the results of the Policy Audit and recommendations for a new generation of public policies and strategies for Europe’s mountain areas [HCC]</p> <p>D7.2 Policy Design Toolkit [HCC]</p> <p>D6.3 Synthesis report, including a Repertoire of Strategic Options [ORIGIN]</p> <p>Additional components:</p> <p>D2.2 Initial set of policy briefs [UNIFI]</p> <p>D5.2 Policy Briefs [UCO]</p> <p>All components are accessible here: https://www.moving-h2020.eu/. No specific restrictions are foreseen for using this background.</p>
Go to Market – IPR Foreground	Contribution and integration of key recommendations into EU post-2027 policy discussion, with an emphasis on Cohesion Policy, CAP, and Territorial Agenda.

Source: MOVING H2020

Use Options

KER's Exploitation route (how the KER will be further exploited): MOVING Conceptual Analytical Framework			
Selected route		Implementing actor	Yes
DI R E C T U S E	Commercialisation: <i>deployment of a novel product/service (offered to the target markets)</i>	One partner	
		A group of partners	
	Contract research (<i>new contracts signed by the research group with external clients</i>)	A partner	
		A group of partners	
	A new research project (<i>application to public funded research programmes</i>)	A partner	X
		A group of partners	X
Implementation of a new university – course (<i>Note that a training course is a service</i>)	A partner		
	A group of partners		
	A new partnership		
IN DI R E C T U S E	Assignment of the IPR	A partner	
		A group of partners	
	Licensing of the IPR	A partner	
		A group of partners	
	Development of a new legislation/standard	A partner	
		A group of partners	
	Spin- off	A partner	
		A group of partners	
By assignment			
By licensing			
Other (<i>please describe</i>)			

Source: MOVING H2020

If more than one option is selected, this should be duly justified e.g., more paths are considered at the same time or final decision not taken yet, etc: A new research project is one of the pre-identified exploitation pathways for the MOVING's project. Individual partners have defined their interests and efforts to identify follow-up research projects, with a particular focus on available funds at the regional and national levels. According to funding opportunities, a group of partners might apply jointly for a project's follow-up.

KER's Exploitation route (how the KER will be further exploited): 23 Mountain Areas Vulnerabilities and Opportunities through Value Chains			
Selected route		Implementing actor	Yes
DI R E C T U	Commercialisation: <i>deployment of a novel product/service (offered to the target markets)</i>	One partner	
		A group of partners	
	Contract research (<i>new contracts signed by the research group with external clients</i>)	A partner	
		A group of partners	
	A new research project (<i>application to public funded research programmes</i>)	A partner	
		A group of partners	
Implementation of a new university – course	A partner		

S E	<i>(Note that a training course is a service)</i>	A group of partners	
		A new partnership	
IN DI R E C T U S E	Assignment of the IPR	A partner	
		A group of partners	
	Licensing of the IPR	A partner	
		A group of partners	
	Development of a new legislation/standard	A partner	
		A group of partners	
	Spin- off	A partner	X
		A group of partners	
By assignment			
	By licensing		
	Other <i>(please describe)</i>		

Source: MOVING H2020

KER's Exploitation route (how the KER will be further exploited): MOVING Policy Tools			
	Selected route	Implementing actor	Yes
DI R E C T U S E	Commercialisation: <i>deployment of a novel product/service (offered to the target markets)</i>	One partner	
		A group of partners	
	Contract research <i>(new contracts signed by the research group with external clients)</i>	A partner	
		A group of partners	
	A new research project <i>(application to public funded research programmes)</i>	A partner	
		A group of partners	
Implementation of a new university – course <i>(Note that a training course is a service)</i>	A partner		
	A group of partners		
	A new partnership		
IN DI R E C T U S E	Assignment of the IPR	A partner	
		A group of partners	
	Licensing of the IPR	A partner	
		A group of partners	
	Development of a new legislation/standard	A partner	
		A group of partners	X
	Spin- off	A partner	
		A group of partners	
By assignment			
	By licensing		
	Other <i>(please describe)</i>		

Source: MOVING H2020

Exploitation roadmap

KER 1: MOVING Conceptual Analytical Framework

The Exploitation Roadmap is a tool designed to help the consortium to identify and plan activities to be performed after the end of the project. The highest risk a consortium faces is not being able to implement the exploitation and dissemination plan and increase the TRL level or go to market, due to lack of resources. The exploitation roadmap is designed to address this risk, mitigate it and pave the way toward use and a stronger impact.

Exploitation roadmap	
Actions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scientific publication on the finalised version of the CAF • Gathering of relevant resources • Follow-up meeting • Uptake of results by research and University partners
Roles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research partners: making use of the KER • Practice partners: promoting the results, testing the KER within regional context/value chains
Milestones	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scientific publication submitted • Meeting minutes
Financials Costs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publication costs • No meeting costs (remote)
Revenues	N/A
Other sources of coverage	Partners resources for covering staff costs and equipment costs (e.g. Internet connection, other research contracts).
Impact in 3-year time	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deepen the understanding of mountain value chains' interactions and dynamics • Contribute to identify key points for leveraging mountain value chains' enhancement

Source: MOVING H2020

KER 2: 23 Mountain Areas Vulnerabilities and Opportunities through Value Chains

The Exploitation Roadmap is a tool designed to help the consortium identify and plan activities to be performed after the end of the project. The highest risk a consortium faces is not being able to implement the exploitation and dissemination plan and increase the TRL level or go to market, due to lack of resources. The exploitation roadmap is designed to address this risk, mitigate it and pave the way toward use and a stronger impact.

Exploitation roadmap	
Actions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Agreement on key tools ● Action plan for bundling the tools together and tailoring to needs ● Definition of governance structure
Roles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Lead partner for coordination ● Technical partners ● Support from scientific partners ● Practice partners for reaching out to users in respective regions and promoting the tools
Milestones	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● General meeting organised ● Roles distributed ● Gathering of tools finalised ● Business plan clearly defined and agreed
Financials	Partners resources for covering staff costs and equipment costs (e.g. Internet connection). Technical infrastructure might be needed.
Costs	
Revenues	
Other sources of coverage	N/A
Impact in 3-year time	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Increase the capacity of mountain value chains' actors to address current and future threats. ● Identify, improve and rollout upgrading strategies for mountain value chains ● Develop a network of regional mountain stakeholders improved skills

Source: MOVING H2020

KER 3: MOVING Policy Tools

The Exploitation Roadmap is a tool designed to help the consortium to identify and plan activities to be performed after the end of the project. The highest risk a consortium faces is not being able to implement the exploitation and dissemination plan and increase the TRL level or go to market, due to lack of resources. The exploitation roadmap is designed to address this risk, mitigate it and pave the way toward use and a stronger impact.

Exploitation roadmap	
Actions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agreement on key tools • Action plan for bundling the tools together and tailoring to needs • Definition of governance structure • Identification of key policy interlocutors • Definition of advocacy strategy
Roles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European-level partners for the European legislative framework • Regional and national level partners for regional/national legislative policy framework
Milestones	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advocacy strategy • Draft of the post-2027 EU legislation • Post-2027 CAP Strategic Plans • Post-2027 Cohesion Policies • National strategy/policies (as relevant)
Financials Costs	Partners resources for covering staff costs and equipment costs (e.g. Internet connection). Travelling costs.
Revenues	N/A
Other sources of coverage	Existing grants (focusing on policy development/advocacy)
Impact in 3-year time	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure that MOVING's results are reflected in a number of key European, national and regional policies and strategies • Raise capacity-building initiatives, programmes and projects to enhance mountain resilience and sustainability

Source: MOVING H2020

KER 1: MOVING Conceptual Analytical Framework

Description of Risks	Risk criticality*	Risk probability*	Risk Grade	Potential intervention	Estimated Feasibility/Success of Intervention*
Partnership Risk Factors					
Disagreement on ownership rules	4	3	12	Grant Agreement clearly defines the ownership of this result.	9
Disagreement on further investments: some partners may leave.	7	5	35	Partners are likely to keep with their promises and plan to exploit this KER as already done during the project implementation period. Mountains are the focus of an increasing number of research and practice-oriented projects for which this KER is needed.	8
CAF having gaps and inconsistencies.	4	7	28	Peer-review of the CAP by MOVING and other external experts. Common agreement.	
Market Risk Factors					
Exploitation disagreement: partners with divergent interests.	4	4	16	Diversified use of this KER is possible and would contribute to a further evolution of the Analytical Framework.	5
Nobody buys the product. Nobody needs it.	4	3	12	The product will be mainly used for non-commercial exploitation, i.e. scientific.	2
Financial/Management Risk Factors					
Lack of endorsement from top management	5	1	5	MOVING partners are part of the top management of their respective organisation	8

Weak exploitation: Inadequate business plan	7	6	42	The current exploitation plan is a first step towards the development of a more concrete business plan.	6
No resources (human and/or financial) secured to make the next step toward exploitation	8	5	40	Search for additional fundings to pursue research activities related to this KER and the MOVING project.	4

*(1 low probability- 10 high probability)

KER 2: 23 Mountain Areas Vulnerabilities and Opportunities through Value Chains

Description of Risks	Risk criticality*	Risk Probability*	Risk Grade	Potential intervention	Estimated Feasibility/Success of Intervention*
Partnership Risk Factors					
Disagreement on further investments: some partners may leave.	4	5	20	Partnership agreement before the project's end. Most results within this KER are open access. Leaving or disagreement with any of the partners would not considerably affect the exploitation route.	9
Disagreement on ownership rules	6	3	18	Partnership agreement before the project's end. The large majority of results within this KER are open-access. Leaving or disagreement from any of the partners would not considerably affect the exploitation route.	8
Partners break out and create competitive products	7	3	21	Partnership agreement before the project's end; definition of different markets	
Technological Risk Factors					
Lack of technological structure to collect all tools together	9	5	45	Contracting technical staff; Deploying existing technical infrastructure and expertise.	7
Market Risk Factors					

Nobody buys the product. Product not tailored to market needs (i.e. language, regional context)	8	6	48	Market segmentation strategies	2
Existence of better competitors	10	7	70	Develop a marketing strategy to convey the added value of these tools (i.e. integration rather than deepness); Continuous improvement of the tools	5
Financial/Management Risk Factors					
Lack of endorsement from top management	9	5	45	Spin-off companies; follow-up exploitation mainly by business and private partners	8
Weak exploitation: Inadequate business plan	6	4	24	Support for business plan development	6
No resources (human and/or financial) secured to make the next step toward exploitation	8	4	32	Search for financial resources to provide adequate resource flowing in the exploitation plan implementation	4

*(1 low probability- 10 high probability)

KER 3: MOVING Policy Tools

Description of Risks	Risk criticality*	Risk probability*	Risk Grade	Potential intervention	Estimated Feasibility/Success of Intervention*
Partnership Risk Factors					
Disagreement on ownership rules	6	3	18	Clarification of ownership rules before project's end	9

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MOUNTAIN VALORISATION THROUGH
INTERCONNECTEDNESS AND GREEN GROWTH

Delays in products' delivery	7	7	49	Careful coordination from the project's top management	8
Market Risk Factors					
Market Demand. Products are not developed in proper timing	9	3	27	Alignment with policy cycle	5
Financial/Management Risk Factors					
No resources (human and/or financial) secured to make the next step toward exploitation	8	5	40	Reliance over advocacy groups within MOVING network and other EU stakeholder networks; Search for resources for KER exploitation; Strategy adaptation to existing resources	8

*(1 low probability- 10 high probability)

